

Starting Point Evaluation Report

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Executive Summary

Introduction

Background to evaluation

- The City of Doncaster Council (CDC) is part of a Health Determinants Research Collaboration (HDRC). This is a collaboration between the council and the University of Sheffield and Sheffield Hallam University to grow research capacity and evidence-based practice to reduce health inequalities and address the wider determinants of health within Doncaster.
- The HDRC works with practitioners to coproduce evaluations of existing interventions to improve understanding of what works locally.
- HDRC researchers, working in conjunction with Starting Point staff, undertook an evaluation of the Starting Point service – previously known as ‘Complex Lives’ - between April 2024 and September 2025. The aim of the evaluation was to explore the impact of the service on person outcomes and on the wider system, as well as to identify any barriers and facilitators to delivering the service.
- In this summary, the key findings from the evaluation are presented. For further findings and more detail, such as direct quotes from participants and examples from the routine data, please see the full-length report.

Background to the service: The Starting Point model - a ‘whole system’ Accountable Care Partnership Approach

- Established in 2017, the Starting Point service is a partnership approach across health, housing and social care services in Doncaster to reduce homelessness and improve outcomes for people with multiple complex needs such as substance misuse, mental ill health and trauma.
- The partnership is underpinned by the Starting Point Alliance, bringing together several key organisations to deliver a coordinated response to support people with multiple needs and to address the wider determinants of homelessness.
- Starting Point provides person centred, long-term support for the causes of homelessness (such as mental health and welfare benefits support) from a multi-agency community hub in Doncaster. Operational delivery is provided by key workers and managers from CDC alongside embedded workers from other services e.g. Department for Work and Pensions (DWP)
- Each person is allocated a key worker who will be their point of contact for support within the service. The support is not time limited and allows time to build trusting relationships between the person and their allocated worker. The type of support reflects people’s differing needs; for example, the key worker can help people to get to GP appointments, support them to access accommodation, arrange utility bills and provide people a consistent presence in their lives that they can ask for help from.

Referral process for Starting Point

- Referrals are usually identified by the outreach team and are discussed at weekly Multidisciplinary Meetings (MDT) meetings which provides an opportunity for input from different partners from across the alliance. Referrals are accepted if a person meets the following criteria:
 - Currently Homeless or at risk of becoming homeless?
 - Support needs not being met by other agencies?
 - Is the individual subject to social exclusion?
 - Is the individual facing multiple disadvantages?

Funding of the Starting Point Service

- The funding model for Starting Point is complex. It is funded by different sources including the local authority and national government initiatives. Each funding stream is for different elements of service delivery and is usually short-term for different time periods. This has implications for continuity of the service and staff recruitment and retention.

Methods

- The evaluation adopted a mixed-methods approach and was conducted in 2024-2025.
- The evaluation included semi structured interviews with Starting Point people (N=9) and with professionals involved in service delivery (N=17). These were supplemented with observations of key meetings (30+ hours). Thematic analysis was undertaken on interview and observation data.
- Analysis was conducted on routine monitoring and outcomes data collected by the service via the Homeless Outcomes Star. The Homeless Outcomes Star is a ten-point outcome measure designed to tailor ongoing service delivery to individual needs. Descriptive analysis was undertaken including Paired Samples T test to analyse changes in outcomes.
- The findings and recommendations were presented at two workshops in August 2025, one with professionals working at the strategic level, and one with the Starting Point operational team, to sense-check and further refine our recommendations.

Key Findings

Complexity of People Backgrounds

- Ninety-seven people were being supported by the Starting Point service in April 2025. Some were rough sleeping, some temporarily housed, and others accommodated. Over two-thirds of the current caseload are males (68%, n=66/97), mirroring national statistics on gender distribution.
- The service supported people from across the age spectrum. People ranged from 21-73 years old. The mean age was 41-years-old. All but two people were classed as White British. None of the 97 people currently receiving support were in employment. 92% were claiming universal credit (n=81/88). Just over half of people were receiving disability benefits (54.5%,

n=48/88). Almost all people were either currently or had previously used drugs (92%, n=80/87). Three quarters of people were still using drugs (n=66/87). Almost half of people were using intravenous drugs (46.9%, n=39/93). Over half of people had historical issues with alcohol (57.1%, n=48/84) and 34 people had current issues with alcohol (40.5%). 60% of people were receiving treatment for substance misuse (n=50/83). The majority of people were smokers (88.65%, n=78/88). This is substantially higher than the UK adult average population of 13.3%.

- Almost two-thirds of people in the service have a diagnosed mental health condition(s) (65%, n=52/80) including anxiety, depression, psychosis, schizophrenia and personality disorders. Over half of people had reported that they have physical health conditions (52.1%, n=49/94). Conditions included leg ulcers, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), brain injury and amputations. For example, almost a quarter needed wound care (22.9%, n=22/96). Some interviewees had been in and out of homelessness over long periods of time. One interview participant was now housed having previously been homeless on and off for over 41 years.
- The multiple needs that people had highlights how people need support beyond accommodation - these other needs require addressing alongside housing needs as part of the pathway to sustainable housing.

Outcomes and Impact of the Service

Impact of the services on Person health and housing outcomes

- It was clear that the Starting Point service was having a positive impact on individual health and housing outcomes. Several interviewees were currently sustaining tenancies which were facilitated by the service. This included some people who had been previously rough sleeping over several years. People reported additional benefits of the service including:
 - Improved finances through receiving support with debt and money management including accessing welfare benefits.
 - Improved physical and mental health through Starting Point facilitating access to healthcare services such as GPs, wound care and drug and alcohol support.
- Improved quality of life through support with the “*little things*”. This included Starting Point providing funds for furniture and clothes, supporting people with everyday tasks such as paying bills or food shopping, providing social and emotional support, booking appointments, providing transport, and arranging access to medical and living aids such as glasses. Support with the “*little things*” was greatly valued, and shows how wider support outside of locating accommodation is required to sustain people not being homeless.
- A small increase in outcome measures was observed from initial baseline assessment to time spent in service via the Homeless Outcomes Star (0.2-0.5 across domains). There were three domains where the change was statistically significant. This means that we are confident that the measurement captured a genuine change rather than it being due to chance. The domains were: Emotional and Mental Health, Managing Accommodation and Tenancy, and Motivation and Taking Responsibility.
- For most domains, the proportion of people who experienced an improvement was between a quarter and a third. For example, 30.9% of people reported feeling they had experienced an

improvement in drug and alcohol misuse and 38.1% reported an improvement in motivation and taking responsibility. The improvement in a range of domains including managing money, self-care and emotional/mental health highlights the range of areas that Starting Point supports people with.

- Alongside improvement, for each domain between 43-55% of people maintained their wellbeing. This indicates the preventative role that Starting Point has in terms of supporting people with complex needs to not deteriorate. About a quarter of people experienced deterioration in each domain. As such, further consideration is needed about why deterioration has occurred, and whether Starting Point can support with these factors or not.
- Reflecting on both the qualitative and quantitative data on the impact of the service, it was evident that whilst there may be relatively small changes on the Outcome Star, individuals viewed Starting Point as having a significant impact on their lives through getting support to meet their health, housing and income needs.

Impact of the service on the wider system

- Professionals felt the service reduced demand on health and public sector services and plugged gaps in provision for individuals with complex needs.

Mechanisms of success

- **Advocacy, flexibility and a Person-centred approach:** Starting Point staff provided a tailored person-centred approach driven by an integrated advocacy role. It provided a collective voice and advocated for the rights of people which was greatly valued by professionals and people.
- **Housing and health system collaboration:** Professionals felt that the alliance agreement created accountability across agencies and supported information sharing, shared ownership of tasks and feeling like a collective to address the broad range of Person needs simultaneously.
- **Bringing services to Starting Point:** Workers from other services such as the DWP were located within Starting Point to provide a 'one stop shop' to help people to access services.
- **Reduce barriers accessing mainstream services:** Access was facilitated to mainstream services by advocating for people and communicating with services on their behalf as well as supporting the use of IT and filling in forms.
- **Building trusted relationships:** As there was no time limit to support, some people remain in the service for several years which supported relationship building. Professionals provided case studies of people who had previously disengaged with services but were now housed and living independently because of the continued support.

Challenges of service delivery

- **Mental health support:** Professionals consistently described how mental health support does not meet the needs of people with complex needs and who have a dual diagnosis of poor

mental health and substance misuse. Gaps were identified for people requiring mental health support who do not meet the severity criteria for secondary mental health services.

- **Barriers in the health system:** It was very challenging for people to access health appointments without the support of a key worker. Barriers in the health system include long waiting times, poor communication between services and rigid appointment times which do not meet the needs of people with complex needs.
- **Challenging behaviours and service disengagement:** Building up relationships and meeting peoples' needs required intensive support from staff. Despite best efforts, some people would exhibit difficult behaviours towards staff or disengage with the service, negatively impacting staff wellbeing, motivation and retention.
- **Difficulties discharging people from the service:** The multitude of challenges facing the cohort means there was no quick fix out of the service and discharge was identified as a key challenge. Professionals felt that people remained in service longer than required which did not always result in independence.
- **Challenges in multidisciplinary working:** There was some perceived duplication of remit such as Outreach and a lack of information sharing from Starting Point to other services. Practitioners questioned the continued buy-in from services to the alliance and felt that the Silver Group could be better attended by mental and primary health providers and those working at strategic level.
- **Flexibility versus consistency of provision:** Professionals felt that the support received depended heavily on the individual support worker which created inconsistencies in delivery. The flexibility of the service adapting to person need is a key mechanism of success, but the findings indicate that it may be beneficial to introduce some baseline expectations within each level of support. External agencies were not clear on the different intervention levels provided by Starting Point. Further information sharing would be beneficial to ensure all agencies understand the remit and ethos of the service, including the support provided and differences between intervention levels.
- **A lack of focus on prevention:** A key challenge were the high numbers of people returning to rough sleeping and a large amount of resource and time is used to support 17 entrenched rough sleepers. It was acknowledged that the service's approach to prevention could be improved. Despite this being a key focus of the alliance, there was currently no action in place to move from a reactive to preventative service.
- **Changing support workers:** Some people, particularly those who had been with the service for a long time, had moved key workers several times depending on the intervention they were receiving. People found this disruptive and confusing, and made it difficult to build trusted relationships.

- **Homelessness stigma within public sector:** There were concerns over attitudes to homelessness and a stigma across the wider council and health services. Perceptions such as a lack of understanding around how long it takes to support people, a preoccupation with the numbers of people on the streets rather than understanding lived experience and that the priority needed to be housing people without an appreciation of the wider drivers of homelessness. Removing stigma remains a key priority for the Starting Point alliance.
- **Intra-workforce challenges:** The challenging nature of the role impacted on staff morale including evidence of compassion fatigue. Challenges included short term contracts impacting the recruitment and retention of skilled staff, inconsistent professional support and poorly defined utilisation of physical space causing tension, and a perceived lack of professionalism in some areas and a need for further training GDPR/data sharing.
- **Protecting the professional identity of embedded worker roles:** Embedded workers were most effective when they spent some of their time in the Starting Point service but remained contracted to and retaining part of their working week with their host organisation including having access to appropriate data systems and line management/supervision (such as the DWP worker who is funded by DWP but spends time in Starting Point).
- **Wider system challenges:** A lack of access to suitable accommodation, rigid medical criteria, and short-term commissioning cycles impacted on the delivery of the service. This requires a system level approach to develop sustainable solutions.

Recommendations:

- Whilst the Starting Point Service is having a positive impact, is an important part of the system, and is greatly valued by professionals and people, some recommendations emerged from the evaluation to support service delivery.
- The following recommendations were coproduced between HDRC researchers and key members of the Starting Point alliance and operational team.
- The recommendations are aimed at different levels including operational and strategic delivery. In this summary, the key recommendations are included with further recommendations included within the main report.

Recommendations for operational delivery:

Starting Point staffing and support

1. Review the support in place for the team and develop clear pathways for accessing support and reporting concerns.
2. Update to the Starting Point Service Standards to ensure that all staff members are clear on their responsibilities.
3. Training to be provided on City of Doncaster Council policy such as Whistleblowing, Code of Conduct, Grievance and complaints.

4. Review the Starting Point roles and responsibilities to ensure they meet the original specification.
5. There is a need to consider options for operational workspace which is currently not fit for purpose. This includes extra space for co-located staff and opportunity to deliver a number of different support services and interventions.
6. Embedded workers should be contracted within their host organisation with access to appropriate systems and supervision.

Starting Point service

1. Develop an accessible space which is practical for use by people, the Starting Point team and other support agencies. This should ensure agencies are under one roof to meet the multiple needs of this complex cohort.
2. Develop a communications strategy and deliver a launch event to provide information to other services and providers around the different roles and functions within the Starting Point Service. This should include wider partners across the council, focusing on committees working at a strategic level.
3. Review of the Starting Point Discharge and Re-Engagement process and allocations process.
4. Explore options for supporting people to become more independent by providing crucial skills and improving people's confidence in managing their lives
5. There needs to be clear communication between people and allocated workers about decisions being made around support and accommodation.
6. Ensure Starting Point service is accessible to all including people from ethnic minorities.

Data insight and systems

1. It is recommended that the data monitoring system is reviewed to ensure it is accessible and recorded in one place to support future commissioning decisions.

Recommendations for strategic delivery

1. Review membership of Starting Point Silver Group to ensure representation from health and strategic level partners. This should include a shared mission statement and visual identity with clear connection between other council groups (such as the Bronze and Gold levels) to ensure appropriate information cascades down.
2. Review Starting Point Alliance agreement to develop a shared agreement outlining roles, responsibilities, and contributions and set baseline expectations for attendance and engagement.
3. Point alliance to review its approach to prevention and create an action plan to move the service from a reactive to a proactive service. This should align with current work being undertaken within the council.
4. Reducing stigma should be a key priority for the Starting Point Alliance and the group should work together to create an action plan to improve this
5. Relaunch the service to partners to ensure everyone is clear on the aims and remit of the service, underpinned by coproduction approach. This could be accompanied by plain-English materials explaining: who the service supports (e.g. homeless, at risk, complex needs), how to

access the service, what support is available and how to refer (including a flowchart with touch points along the journey).

6. There is a need to develop the health inclusion support offer. This should be underpinned by a system approach which involves both housing and health practitioners. MDT meetings to discuss complex cases could be considered.
7. The service (alongside system partners) should continue lobbying for the development of appropriate housing in the borough.
8. The strategic alliance/commissioners need to consider how to maximise funding especially concurrent funding adopting a more 'alliance' commissioning model.

Introduction

Health Determinants Research Collaboration

City of Doncaster Council (CDC) has been awarded funding by the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) for the Health Determinants Research Collaboration (HDRC). HDRC Doncaster is one of 30 collaborations across the country which aims to help local authorities to become more research active and embed a culture of evidence-based decision making within everyday practice. Hosted by Doncaster Council, in collaboration with the University of Sheffield and Sheffield Hallam University, the aim of the programme in Doncaster is to grow research capacity and evidence-based practice to reduce health inequalities and address the wider determinants of health. Part of the remit of the HDRC is to work with practitioners to coproduce evaluations of existing interventions to improve understanding of what works locally.

Background to evaluation

Homelessness is a major global health and policy issue which has a great impact on health and wellbeing and the wider healthcare system. In England (UK), 298,430 households, including 104,460 families with children, became homeless or were at risk of homelessness between April 2022 and March 2023 (Inside Housing, 2023), a figure which has risen by 74% since 2010 (Butler, 2023). Homelessness remains a significant and costly public health problem, with annual costs on the UK economy of approximately £30,000 per person, or £1 billion, each year (Department of Communities and Local Government, 2012).

The detrimental health impacts of homelessness are wide ranging and complex. Homeless individuals have substantially higher rates of mortality, morbidity and ill health than the general population, including higher rates of mental illness, heart disease, infections (e.g. tuberculosis, HIV), substance misuse, hospital readmissions and suicide (e.g. Gutwinski et al, 2021, Lewer et al, 2021, Marcus et al, 2018, Morrison, 2009, Hwang et al, 2009). The relationship between homelessness and health is inherently complex and intertwined, as whilst homelessness is a key driver of poor health, poor health is also a driver for homelessness. The drivers of homelessness are socially determined and intrinsically linked to structural inequalities and poverty (Bramley, Fitzpatrick, 2018). Psychosocial issues such as family breakdown and substance misuse are exacerbated by structural conditions such as socioeconomic status and the accessibility and affordability of suitable housing (Mago et al, 2013). This complex set of needs frequently results in individuals falling between the gaps of services which are often focused on supporting one particular issue such as substance misuse (Public Health England, 2018), rather than providing support across the wider determinants of health.

Recognising the increasing prevalence and health impact of homelessness has resulted in increased policy attention on homelessness prevention. The National Homelessness Reduction Act (2017) places duties on local authorities to act earlier in the pathway to provide support to all individuals affected or at risk of homelessness. The act also encourages joint working across agencies (such as local authorities, the police and hospitals) to ensure timely referral of individuals who present as at risk of homelessness (Shelter, 2018). The strategy for ending rough sleeping by the Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities (2022) further advocates for joint working to deliver systems change to end homelessness. Despite increased policy attention on the importance of systems approaches to preventing homelessness and for tackling widening inequalities, there is a lack of evidence on the

impact of such action. Given the impact of homelessness, there is an urgent need for further research to understand effective strategies to reduce homelessness through preventive support (Marshall, Bibby, 2020).

Rationale for evaluation

Background to the service: The Complex Lives Alliance delivery model - a 'whole system' Accountable Care Partnership Approach

Established in 2017, the Starting Point service is a partnership approach across health and social care services in Doncaster, UK, to reduce homelessness and improve outcomes for those with multiple complex needs such as substance misuse, mental ill health and trauma. Delivered primarily by Doncaster Council, the approach involves the integration of services across the council, RDasH (NHS Community Foundation Trust), DBTH (Doncaster and Bassetlaw Teaching Hospital NHS Foundation Trust), Primary Care Doncaster, the Probation Service, Nacro, South Yorkshire Police, DWP, Liaison and Diversion and other community, faith, voluntary sector and housing providers to deliver wrap around support to the most disadvantaged people in Doncaster.

At the core of the operational model is the Starting Point multidisciplinary delivery team with integrated posts across the alliance including Mental Health, Substance Misuse, DWP and Housing. The service operates out of a multi-agency community hub in Doncaster to deliver holistic, wrap around support focused on prevention. Team members work together to engage, triage and provide a strong accommodation and support plan for people with a combination of mutually enforcing challenges. The team works flexibly and provides personalised responses to individual strengths and needs. Multi agency discussions take place at MDT weekly meetings to discuss individual cases and agree appropriate actions. Specific areas of focus include monitoring of:

- Prison releases
- Hospital discharges
- Potential evictions
- Partnership working and early intervention
- New rough sleepers to prevent homelessness becoming entrenched

Previous evaluation findings

Previous evaluation of the Starting Point service undertaken the Policy, Insights and Change Team in Doncaster Council (2019) included quantitative analysis of routinely collected data and an economic evaluation to assert costs. The evaluation findings highlight that the approach is making savings across the majority of indicators. Analysis of quantitative outcomes data also showed an average overall improvement in all areas/domains. Although the findings of the internal evaluation were useful, practitioners felt that they lacked understanding of the lived experience of people and the impact of the service on the wider healthcare system. It was also felt that a more up to date evaluation was needed. To fill this gap in evidence the Starting Point team at Doncaster Council requested that the HDRC team undertake a service evaluation to inform future service delivery and commissioning decisions. As well as informing local decision making, the findings are likely to be useful to other services wishing to develop integrated services delivering homelessness prevention.

Methods

The evaluation adopted a mixed methods approach. It used semi structured interviews with people who received the Starting Point service (N=9) and with professionals involved in service delivery (N=17). These were supplemented with observations of key meetings (30+ hours) alongside analysis of routine outcomes data collection by the service. The findings were brought together to draw out key learning points which will inform the delivery of the service as well as having the potential to inform service delivery in other localities.

The overall aims of the evaluation were:

- To explore the impact of the service on user health and housing outcomes
- To explore the impact of the service on the wider health system
- Identify any barriers and facilitators to successful implementation of the service

The objectives of the evaluation were to:

- Conduct semi structured interviews with people currently accessing the Starting Point service and professionals involved in service delivery
- Conduct observation of meetings which bring stakeholders across the system together
- Analyse interview and observation data using thematic analysis
- Analyse routine data using descriptive analysis
- Integrate the qualitative and quantitative data
- Share learning from evaluation to support development of the service

Interviews with people

The research team conducted 9 interviews with people who were currently receiving support from the Starting Point service to understand the impact of the service on housing and health outcomes. Recruitment was supported by our Doncaster council project partners who facilitated recruitment and dissemination of study information and information sheets to potential participants. A member of the Starting Point team explained the study, shared project materials and took written consent from people before seeking permission to refer them onto the University research team to arrange an interview. As people often did not have mobile phones or home addresses a pragmatic approach to recruitment was undertaken. The researcher spent two full days at the Changing Lives hub where interested participants were able to “drop in” to take part in a face-to-face interview. Where possible, dates and times were prearranged by Doncaster Council staff who were able to locate individuals in the town centre and bring them to the office for the interview if required. Consent was checked again at the start of each interview and participants had the opportunity to ask questions about the study and their involvement. Participation was entirely voluntary; only those who had expressed interest in taking part and who read the information sheet and completed a consent were eligible to participate. Interviews took place face to face in the Changing Lives building. Each participant received a £10 voucher for their participation in an interview.

Interviews with practitioners

To understand how the Starting Point service has had an impact on the wider system, the research team conducted 17 interviews with staff who involved in service delivery or who have

experience/knowledge of the service. The study was introduced to staff via an email from the Starting Point manager. Those who were interested in taking part were referred onto the researchers who shared project materials and made arrangements for the interview if appropriate. A flexible approach to the timing and process of interviews was undertaken to minimise disruption to busy work schedules. Interviews took place via video call.

Observation of key meetings

To further understand the impact of the service on the wider system and any challenges and learning from implementation of the service we conducted ethnographic data collection through the observation of key meetings where decisions around the service are made. The researcher observed over 30 hours of operational (e.g. Starting Point MDTs), strategic (e.g. Starting Point Silver Group), and system level meetings (e.g. Homelessness Board) to help provide context and understanding about the service, the wider housing and health system, key stakeholders, planned activities, current and future progress and any barriers and issues encountered. Observational data was captured using a template developed to capture meeting activities and atmospheric observations. The Starting Point manager identified relevant meetings for observation and contacted the meeting chair on behalf of the researchers to seek permission for them to attend and observe the meetings. If they agreed, an information sheet was sent to attendees alongside the meeting agenda with a statement which explains the purpose of the observation and an option to opt out of the observation if required. At the start of the observation the researcher further explained about the research and the purpose of the observation, including rights to anonymity and confidentiality, and offered participants the opportunity to opt out of the observation if required. As well as sensitising researchers to the decision-making context, observations were also used to identify potential participants for the practitioner interviews.

Qualitative data analysis

With participants’ consent, interviews were audio recorded and transcribed verbatim using the SCHARR Transcribers Service. An inductive thematic analysis was conducted on the data, informed by Braun and Clarke’s (2006) six stage thematic analysis approach. This involves: Step 1: Become familiar with the data, Step 2: Generate initial codes, Step 3: Search for themes, Step 4: Reviewing themes, Step 5: Defining themes, Step 6: Write-up. The research team each read a small selection of transcripts, before meeting to discuss initial codes and themes. The team then developed a coding framework and applied this to the transcripts using NVivo software. The research team met regularly to discuss coding and to amend the coding framework as appropriate. Thematic analysis was conducted on the observation data using the same approach.

Quantitative

Doncaster Council records routine data including demographics, service use and changes in wellbeing (measured by the Homelessness Outcomes Star). Data is collected from each individual every three months as part of routine service processes. Each individual is assigned a unique identifier by the service. The data is kept on a secure service-based database hosted by Doncaster Council. The team used this database to produce an Excel sheet capturing the information collected on people who were current people of the service in April 2025. This encrypted spreadsheet was saved onto Doncaster

Council Secure Servers. The data was then downloaded and saved on the University of Sheffield secure drive for analysis.

Quantitative data analysis

Descriptive analysis was conducted on the routine data. This included frequencies for the demographic variables and Paired Samples T test to analyse improvements in mental wellbeing measured via changes on the baseline and most recent Outcome Measure.

Consolidation workshops

We presented the findings and recommendations from the evaluation in two workshops to system leaders and the operational team to sense check our findings and further refine our recommendations.

Ethics

Ethical approval was granted by the Sheffield Centre for Health and Related Research (SCHARR), University of Sheffield ethics committee [058705] [01.05.2024].

Findings: Background

Demographics of People Supported by the Service

Ninety-seven people were being supported by Starting Point service in April 2025. These people were at different stages of their journey- some were rough sleeping, some temporarily housed and others accommodated. The Service Manager reported that this quantity is the norm with the service caseload being relatively stable at between 90-105 people at any time.

Over two-thirds of the current caseload are males (68%, n=66/97). Less than a third are females (31.9%, n=31/97). This reflects the national statistics that consistently demonstrated that there are more males rough sleeping than females.

The service supported people from across the age spectrum. People were aged 21-73 years old. The mean age was 41-years-old. It is likely that people will have different needs depending on their age.

All but two people were classed as White British. One person was Black African, and one person was of mixed-ethnicity. All but one person was from the United Kingdom. This person was from Rwanda. Within Doncaster, 15.6% of the population are non-White British and 10% were born overseas. Starting Point is less ethnically diverse than Doncaster as a place ([How life has changed in Doncaster: Census 2021](#)). Consequently, it is important for the service to reflect whether there are potential people of different ethnicities who would benefit from accessing Starting Point but for whatever reason are not being reached by the service.

The vast majority of people considered themselves heterosexual (96.6%, n=84/87, 96.6%). Two people identified as bisexual, and one person was a lesbian.

11.3% people were married or had a partner (Married: n=1/97 and Partners n=10/97). Within the qualitative interviews, some people spoke about having older children or siblings whereas some staff and people spoke of some people not having significant people in their lives. For example, Starting Point staff being named as next of kin or having to organise people's funerals.

None of the 97 people currently receiving support were in employment. 92% were claiming universal credit (n=81/88). Just over half of people were receiving disability benefits (54.5%, n=48/88). A couple of people were recorded as having other incomes such as pensions or Employment Support Allowance.

4.5% of people accessing the service were care leavers (n=4/93). Up to 25% of the UK adult homeless population are thought to have been care leavers ([Care Leavers and care-experienced young people | Home For Good](#)) so this proportion is lower than anticipated. Further consideration is needed about whether there is a gap in referrals, or it could be that there is other provision within the area which is supporting care leavers to prevent them becoming homeless.

Complexity of People Supported by the Service

It was clear that the Starting Point cohort were dealing with a multitude of vulnerabilities and complex needs alongside their housing situations. These included mental health issues such as depression and anxiety, substance misuse, domestic abuse, physical health issues, movement in and out of prison, adverse childhood experiences, relationship breakdown, learning difficulties and trauma. Such experiences both contributed to and compounded their housing situations. Some interviewees had

been in and out of homelessness over long periods of time with one interview participant, who was currently housed through the service, having previously been homeless on and off for over 41 years. This multilayering of complex issues created a cycle of rough sleeping that was described as being difficult to escape:

“I think there’s multiple issues... You know we’ve got individuals that you know are in difficult relationships. Abusive relationships, they’ve suffered childhood trauma. That has a big impact and a knock-on effect to them, then going on to use substances, to offending. People that have lost every option that they’ve got in terms of accommodation. They’ve been in every supported housing that we’ve got available to us in Doncaster and it’s ended badly because the right support not been in place, so they return back to rough sleeping” (Interview, Professional, 5)

People were living in a variety of types of accommodation. A little over a quarter (25.7% n=25/97) were rough sleeping, highlighting how the service supports rough sleepers and it can take time to help them into accommodation. Just over a quarter were in Housing First accommodation (26.8%, n=26/97). The third most common was [Single Homeless Accommodation Project \(SHAP\)](#) (13.4%, n=13/97). Other types of accommodation included people staying in hostels and sofa surfing. There were a small number of people (e.g. fewer than 3 people per type) in prison, mental health hospitals and supported accommodation. The range of accommodation types highlights the complexity of need of people being supported by Starting Point and the range of accommodation types available within the system. Many of the people were in temporary accommodation and needing support to access more permanent, suitable accommodation. But given people’s needs and the availability of housing options it may take a few ‘moves’ for people to reach the optimum housing option.

Addiction and Substance Misuse

The majority of people accessing the Starting Point service had current or former addiction and substance misuse issues, which often occurred alongside poor mental health. This was evident through both the analysis of routine data and the qualitative interviews:

“...homelessness and substance misuse, kind of come hand in hand... it is staggeringly high, I would say probably 80-90%” (Interview, Professional, 14)

Almost all people were either currently or had previously used drugs (92%, n=80/87). Three quarters of people were still using drugs (n=66/87). Almost half of people were using intravenous drugs (46.9%, n=39/93). Over half of people had historical issues with alcohol (57.1%, n=48/84) and 34 people had current issues with alcohol (40.5%). 60% of people were receiving treatment for substance misuse (n=50/83).

The majority of people were smokers (88.65%, n=78/88). This is substantially higher than the UK adult average population of 13.3%

(<https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/healthandsocialcare/healthandlifeexpectancies/bulletins/adultsmokinghabitsingreatbritain/2021>).

Whilst smoking may be less of a priority for people to address given other needs, it may be having a detrimental impact on people’s physical health.

Given the high numbers of people with current or historic experiences of substance misuse, it indicates that Starting Point has a role in supporting people with substance misuse issues and supporting them

to navigate services to receive sufficient support. This issue is explored subsequently when we discuss the challenges of accessing mental health services for the Starting Point cohort.

Mental Health Needs

Almost two-thirds of people had a diagnosed mental health condition(s) (65%, n=52/80). Conditions included anxiety, depression, psychosis, schizophrenia and personality disorders. This indicates that people have mental health needs that may require healthcare support from both Primary and Secondary health care services. This issue is discussed later in the report in respect of providing mental health care to the cohort. A small number of people had acquired brain injury (7.4%, n=7/94). Some of the people discussed how this caused difficulty with memory and thus managing life administration and finances which had implications for the support they needed from Starting Point. A small number were eligible for Section 117 funding. This is a form of financial support to provide aftercare following detention under the Mental Health Act (6.6% n=6/91). 14.3% of people were assessed to have eligible needs under the Care Act (n=13/91). These both have implications for service delivery as have conditions attached for follow-up care. There were concerns from within the service that a greater number of people may have a condition or have the needs that would make them eligible for support but have not been assessed because of difficulty of engaging with services. This leaves Starting Point managing people’s needs without them having a formal diagnosis or getting the additional support they would be eligible for.

Physical Health Conditions

Over half of people had reported that they have physical health conditions (52.1%, n=49/94). The conditions included leg ulcers, COPD, brain injury and amputations. For example, almost a quarter of people needed wound care (22.9%, n=22/96). Some of the conditions had been exacerbated by people’s circumstances such as the difficulty of keeping wounds clean when rough sleeping. The majority of people were registered with a GP (80.9%, n=76/94). However, this also indicates that a fifth of people were not registered with a GP and this something that Starting Point does support people with. Less than a fifth of people were recorded as being registered with a dentist (19.4%, n=18/93).

Needs of People Supported by the Service

People accessing the Starting Point service had a range of needs, with most people having multiple needs. Almost everyone had needs related to their housing, substance misuse issues and mental health (Table 1). These needs are intertwined, for example someone may be struggling with their mental health and using substances to help them cope which makes it difficult to sustain their housing. Over two-thirds of people had contact with the criminal justice system and/or been in prison. Just over half of people had physical health needs. A small number of people were identified to have needs in line with the Care Act or engaging in sex work. The multiple needs that people had highlights the complexity and how people need support beyond accommodation - these other needs require addressing alongside housing needs as part of the pathway to sustainable housing.

Table 1- Needs of people when accessing Starting Point

Needs	Percentage (%)	Number (n)
Substance Misuse	92.3%	84/91
Housing Needs	89.7%	87/97

Mental Health Needs	86.5%	77/89
Offending background	67.7%	65/96
Physical Health Needs	57.1%	52/91
Care Act Needs	14.6%	14/96
Sex Worker	13.4%	13/97

Please note there are different numbers for each need as depended on how well completed the variable was.

Figure 2- Types of need when accessing Starting Point

Core Components of the Service and Elements of Support

The Starting Point service began by providing acute support to ‘tent city’ – a collection of tents housing homeless individuals within the city centre. After consultation with health colleagues, it was felt that there was a gap in current provision for those experiencing rough sleeping and multiple complex needs with a need to: “*work with other partners to try and simplify how they can navigate through that complexity*” (Interview, Professional, 10). There was a recognition that the current provision which focused on simply housing people, did not address the diversity of individuals facing homelessness:

“So obviously at the time that I become involved it was on the back of the massive issue of the tented protest. The fact that we had so many people in one place. Just the risk around that area was a concern but I think it also highlighted where there were blockages within the systems. Aged systems, historic systems that didn’t meet the support needs of the individuals

anymore. Our individuals that we deal with day in, day out, don't fit into tick boxes. And I think it's very easy to pick somebody up and stick them into a unit. That's what I'll say whether it's you know hostel, e-bed, private rent, whatever that accommodation type is it's so easy to pick them up and hide them away in a unit, but you are not addressing anything. You are not addressing that support need. You are not helping them recover. You are not helping them heal" (Professional, 5)

The Starting Point service was developed in recognition of this need, and first began with a small rough sleeper response team focusing on the 'tent city' cohort in the centre. The service has since evolved and supports people by delivering street-based interventions to rough sleepers, all the way through to supporting people to maintain and sustain accommodation independently. The overall aim of the service is to support people to navigate housing and support services whilst promoting independence, equality and connecting with relevant services to meet their individual needs.

The Starting Point service recognises that there is a need for bespoke interventions that meet individuals where they are, both environmentally and in their personal journey. These interventions are delivered by different roles within the team. This includes:

- **Outreach (street-based intervention):** The aim of the Outreach team is to identify people who are rough sleeping and help them off the streets as quickly as possible to reduce the impact on the individual and the community. Outreach staff will then triage individuals to appropriate support, either within the wider alliance or in Starting Point, if the referral is considered appropriate. This approach is considered a short-term street-based intervention focused on early intervention and prevention. Tasks include providing an assertive outreach approach to support rough sleepers in Doncaster, actively engaging with people within the city centre and across the borough. The outreach team acts as a visible presence to identify and support new and existing rough sleepers.
- **Navigators:** A less assertive approach to support levels, focusing on the worker helping people access the services they need. The role of the Navigator is to support individuals to connect with accommodation and support services, whilst developing individual support plans and short-term goals for the person. The Navigator will support people to navigate the different services and support them to take the first steps to accessing the support.
- **Starting Point Case Worker:** These are specialist caseworkers that co-ordinate a multi-agency approach to managing risk and safeguarding concerns, as well as person-centred support for the individual concerned. Those with the highest level of risk and need - including self-neglect, exploitation and unmanaged vulnerabilities - will be supported by the Specialist Caseworker.

Each person is allocated a key worker who is their point of contact for support within the Starting Point service. Allocations are considered around levels of risk and need, as well as considering the fundamentals for developing trusting relationships. People will only be discharged from the service if the person's support needs are being met by another agency, or if they leave the area. The support is not time limited and allows time to build trusting relationships between the person and their allocated worker.

Starting Point staff described the role of a key worker as providing an important liaison function between them and housing and support services across the Starting Point Alliance. The main components of the role include:

- Regular engagement with people to understand their ongoing support needs (e.g., whether they have physical or mental health issues or vulnerabilities, types of support or accommodation required) as well as reviewing what is important to them at that time.
- Liaising with housing and support services across the Alliance to broker access to services, including making onward referrals and supporting people to attend appointments.
- Advocating for Person needs across the alliance and within the wider council.
- Regular communication/coordination with the cohort and housing and support services.

The key components of the service and provision of support are reflected in the following principles, that underline the work of the service The description is written by the service themselves:

What do we do?

The team provides the capacity to identify, engage, triage, and provide personalised accommodation and support plans to meet individual needs. We are focused on recovery and resettlement working alongside people to achieve their goals.

How we do this?

HOPE	We help to build individual self-esteem so that you are able to recognise your self-worth, and see that change is possible. We will lend our hope to anyone who needs it, and empower you to make use of your own assets.
CONNECTION	We invest in you, working to understand your life, needs and motivations with no judgement. We help navigate and connect you with services and groups in your local community. We support you to make the connections that will improve your wellbeing, self-worth and independence.
RELATIONSHIPS	We will support you to build, rebuild and maintain healthy and positive relationships. We will do this with the respect and understanding of the relationships that are important to you. We can help you to recognise harmful and damaging relationships with others including relatives, friends, and other associates.
INCLUSION	We support you to explore your own needs and goals for a more positive future. We promote individual choice and control, giving you the agency to make the decisions on your own life. We provide the guidance to make you the experts in your own lives.
FLEXIBILITY	People are at the heart of everything we do. We deliver at your pace, without any time constraints or schedules. We offer a community front door where you can access support from the team when needed. We will tailor support based on individual need, which will remain open ended for as long as is needed.

RIGHTS	We will advocate for you, and what matters to you. We will provide you with all the guidance you need to understand what you are entitled to, and help you decide which options are best for you. We will encourage your independence, whilst promoting autonomy and choice.
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Starting Point Strategic Alliance

The Starting Point Team is underpinned by the Starting Point Alliance, which brings together several key organisations from across Housing and support services. The partnership aims to deliver a coordinated response to support people with multiple needs and the wider determinants of homelessness.

The Alliance is a partnership agreement that is supported by the following organisations: Doncaster City Council, South Yorkshire Integrated Care Board (ICB), Rotherham Doncaster and South Humber NHS Foundation Trust, Doncaster Bassetlaw Teaching Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, Primary Care Doncaster, Department of Work and Pensions, South Yorkshire Police, St Leger Homes, Yorkshire and Humber Probation Service and other community, health and social care services.

Senior leaders from across the Alliance also attend the monthly Starting Point Silver Group, which is a forum that aims to provide strategic leadership to support policy change. More information is provided on the Alliance, including the benefits and challenges of partnership working, and are discussed later in the report.

Embedded Roles

A key aspect of the Starting Point service is that the team host a number of embedded roles from across the partnership. This allows for people to access multiple services in one to provide wrap-around support.

At the time of the interviews, this included a representative from the Department of Work and Pensions, a mental health social worker, Home Options Officer, Peer Support Worker, Positive Pathways Worker and a Drug and Alcohol worker. Workers are embedded within the service and provide person centred support within one location. For more information on the impact and challenges of the embedded worker role, see later sections in the report.

Funding and Interventions

The funding model for Starting Point is complex and brought together through a “*jigsaw puzzle of different funding sources*” (Interview, Professional, 1). The breakdown of funding streams and the different interventions offered by the service are provided below:

Table 2 - Sources of Funding

Funding Area	Project/Team	Service Area Roles and Responsibilities
Homeless Prevention Grant and	Core Complex Lives Team (Starting Point)	The core team is a dedicated team of frontline caseworkers working with people facing homelessness living complex lives. These are people with a combination of mutually reinforcing challenges including homelessness, drug, and alcohol use, offending

Doncaster Council		behaviour, mental ill health, poor physical health, including sex workers. The team are their consistent point of contact and champion in co-defining their assets, needs and outcomes.
Rough Sleeper Drug and Alcohol Treatment Grant (Public Health Owned)	Outreach	Outreach Workers are responsible for the delivery of a knowledgeable, creative, and highly personalised support service to people who are rough sleeping or at risk of rough sleeping. They negotiate solutions to access suitable housing and offering opportunities to engage with a range of other services to promote good health and wellbeing and reduce the risk of future homelessness.
Rough Sleeper Initiative (RSI) Allocated funding from Central Government	Housing First	Housing First is a housing and support approach which: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gives people who have experienced homelessness and chronic health and social care needs a stable home from which to rebuild their lives. • Provides intensive, person-centred, holistic support that is open-ended. • Places no conditions on individuals; however, they should desire to have a tenancy. <p>The model provides a permanent offer of independent stable accommodation and open-ended wrap around support</p>
SHAP Funding allocation Allocated funding from Central Government	Single Homelessness Accommodation Programme (SHAP)	SHAP aims to address the rough sleeping need within a local area's individual pathway. The programme will be directed at two groups in particular: those with the longest histories of rough sleeping, or the most complex needs, to help them recover from rough sleeping and its associated traumas; as well as vulnerable young people (age 18-25) at risk of homelessness or rough sleeping to prevent them from becoming street homeless. Supported and specialist housing and Housing First accommodation suitable for these groups will be within scope of the programme. Funding will be targeted at those areas where data suggests there is need for further accommodation for SHAP's target groups.
SHIP Funding Allocated funding from	Supported Housing Improvement Programme (SHIP)	The Supported Housing Improvement Programme (SHIP) is an England-wide 20-million-pound Government funded programme led by the Department of Levelling Up, Housing & Communities (DLUHC). The programme

<p>Central Government</p>		<p>is a 3-year funded programme covering the financial years 2022 to 2025.</p> <p>DLUHC describe the overriding objective of the programme is to raise standards and tackle instances of poor practice in supported accommodation by enabling local authorities to deliver on the following with the funding received:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drive up standards of accommodation and support. • Improve value for money of supported housing. • Implement improved management of supported housing. • Improve knowledge of local supply and demand. • Intervene in Housing Benefit applications relating to new provision, where it is unsuitable, does not meet local need or does not meet local authorities’ expected standards. • Support neighbourhoods and communities affected by the symptoms of poor-quality provision.
<p>Rough Sleeper Initiative (RSI)</p> <p>Allocated funding from Central Government</p>	<p>Assessment Hub</p>	<p>The overarching aim of the service is to reduce the number of individuals sleeping rough in Doncaster. This will include entrenched rough sleepers and to reduce the numbers of people returning to the streets.</p> <p>In order to achieve the above aim, the Hub will need to deliver a multi-agency approach which facilitates rapid assessment of individual’s needs. This will include suitable housing options, substance misuse and health (physical and mental), benefits and meaningful use of time.</p> <p>The Hub will enable someone to move-on to sustainable accommodation with access to necessary services/agencies. This will be done as part of a multi-agency approach with wrap around support in place.</p>
<p>Integrated Care Board and RDASH</p>	<p>Mental Health Rough Sleeper Project</p>	<p>The policy direction in the NHS Long Term Plan acknowledges the importance of a focus on homelessness and issues related to supporting people with Starting Point. There is focus on health inequalities specifically relating to Homelessness and commitment to improve access to specialist homelessness NHS</p>

		<p>mental health support, integrated with existing outreach services. In addition, it also refers a focus on severe mental health problems and commitment to a community-based offer including psychological therapies.</p>
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A key aspect of the role of embedded workers is to advocate for this approach and highlight the need for continued investment from their contracted organisations. Since embedded workers remain contracted to and funded by their organisations - such as the Department for Work and Pensions - this approach is a relatively cost-effective means of delivering support. However, it requires buy in from contracting organisations. Each funding stream has different start and end points which has implications for continuity of the service and staff recruitment and retention. For more information on the challenges of this approach, please see 'Challenges' section.

Referral Process

The service utilises the following referral criteria:

- **Currently Homeless or at risk of becoming Homeless** – Are they currently rough sleeping, sofa surfing or in temporary accommodation. The individual may be on notice, risk of eviction or leaving an institution (prison/hospital)
- **Are support needs being met by other agencies?** – Risk of duplicating work or other agencies pulling out of support when it is clearly needed
- **Is the individual subject to social exclusion?** - Social exclusion is the process in which individuals are blocked from (or denied full access to) various rights, opportunities and resources that are normally available to members of a different group, and which are fundamental to social integration. (e.g., housing, employment, healthcare, civic engagement, democratic participation, and due process)
- **Is the individual facing multiple disadvantage?** – People facing multiple disadvantages are those with a combination of problems including homelessness

Referrals are discussed at the weekly MDT meetings which provide an opportunity for input from different partners from across the alliance. Potential referrals are usually identified by the outreach team who directly respond to intelligence and information about the location of rough sleepers. However, at the time of conducting quantitative analysis, the service did not hold data on the number of people referred and of referral routes. It was suggested that this could be an area of development to ensure the service is reaching its target cohorts and was taken forward and implemented by the service. As well as discussing new referrals, Alliance members are invited to bring cases for discussion and utilise the services around the table to problem solve or co-ordinate support around a specific person. This forum also provides opportunity for the partnership to share regular updates on individuals progress and coordinate support and actions.

A key point emphasised by the service managers in respect of referrals was that Starting Point was not a service for people who already had agencies involved that are able to meet their needs. Referrers are often asked to reflect on their practice where they feel they can no longer support the individual and want them to be considered for Starting Point support. Non-engagement is not viewed as a reason to refer into the service. It was meant to be a service for people who were not connected to other

services and have no support in place. These individuals are often those who are excluded from services or not known to them in any capacity at all. It was felt important to maintain that core distinction.

Outcomes and Impact of the Service

Impact of the Services on Person Health, Wellbeing and Housing Outcomes

It was clear from the interviews and observation data that the Starting Point service was having a positive impact on individual health and housing outcomes. Several interviewees were currently sustaining tenancies which were facilitated by the service. This included some people who had been previously rough sleeping over several years.

People described a variety of other outcomes as a result of the service, including:

- Accessing support with debt and money management and setting up benefits.
- Improved physical and mental health through facilitating access to services such as GPs, dentists, drug and alcohol support.
- People also described “*little things*” provided by the service such as: funds for furniture and clothes, support with everyday tasks such as paying bills or food shopping, providing social and emotional support, booking appointments, providing transport, and arranging access to medical and living aids such as glasses.

Although considered small, the impact of such support was extremely valued by both people and wider professionals:

“Then I got my house. [Name of support worker] took us shopping and all that. She bought my TV, well the TV she bought is broke, bought the Hoover, what else, microwave. Toaster. She bought us clothes and all that you know what I mean. Yeah she took me shopping. She’s, normally, she’s brilliant man”
(Interview, Person, 9)

“Every time I come in as well, I always get a brew off of them and stuff like that, so yeah, I know it’s nothing, but it’s not, I think it’s those little things that all add up” (Interview, Person, 7)

“...again supporting people getting to appointments, providing bus passes, but we can also access things like the innovation fund, which is invaluable, in terms of, we use it to get mobile phones, things that kind of increase the quality of people’s recovery like gym passes and things like that, which is massively invaluable and fantastic for people.” (Interview, Professional, 14)

For example, support with everyday tasks such as paying bills or reading letters was a huge source of support for some people who struggled to undertake such tasks independently:

“I come to Starting Point sometimes, you know, when I get letters and I find it difficult to digest, you know, some of the mail that you get. So, they’ve helped, you know, they’ve helped me. Helped me, like, read the letters.”
(Interview, Person, 6)

“Well, they found me a bungalow, somewhere to keep the roof over my head. They've taken me places in the car, because I don't drive. And, well they've done a lot of things really. She's helped me with all my bills. Well, they've all done it to me.... They put the forms in, and I'm on the waiting list. I've been accepted” (Interview, Person, 3)

People were particularly positive about the support they had received with their benefit applications, provided by the embedded worker from the Department for Work and Pensions. Some people were unaware of the support they were entitled to, whilst others previously struggled to access the benefit system due to issues such as memory loss or other vulnerabilities which made it difficult to attend structured appointments. The worker also described how they had overturned sanctions on people on multiple occasions after they had stopped communicating with benefits services due to poor mental health (see ‘Mechanisms of Success’):

“She works at DWP and she's amazing because, 'cause with my memory, I'd probably be sanctioned to death and everything[...] without her, I'd be locked out of my own account and she deals with all of my stuff for Universal Credit. She sorted it out for me to get capability to work. Work capability or something. So my money's gone up, And then she helped me fill out my PIP forms, and she sent them off. So everything I do is through [name of worker] with the job centre. Otherwise I'd be screwed, basically.” (Interview, Person, 7)

“...everything's been perfect. They've helped me do my benefits, filling out paperwork. I'm on universal credit, but they did help me fill in other forms, and they helped get some benefits.” (Interview, Person, 6)

“I getting my money and all that, get my PIP [...] Well over a few month ago, she says oh you should be getting extra, extra money. Thinking oh, I didn't know what she meant like, you know what I mean, and that's when I started getting £900.” (Interview, Person, 9)

In addition, professionals described how the service had a positive impact on physical and mental health, including facilitating access to appointments, medication and wound care, which was considered vital support:

“To see the lady now, she's a different person, she's just like your granny that shops at Marks & Spencer's, you wouldn't think there was anything wrong compared to old time, yeah I think if in that sort of case if we hadn't have got involved, she wouldn't be living a normal life and she is living a normal life now, because really all she needed was that bipolar medication.” (Interview, Professional, 15)

“So the Starting Point service pay for the wound care, wound care is massive just in terms of, it definitely is savings lives, but quality of lives you know reducing the amount of people that are going have amputations, reduces the impact of the NHS, the kind of costs of that, peoples kind of independence... that's massive, getting people in dentists, doctors, that kind of stuff, is huge and again, we did lot of work with the [organisation] and a lot of other GP surgeries and trying to remove some of those barriers, because you have got ring up at 8 o'clock, to make an appointment but we don't start until 9, people

don't have phones and chances are ringing is going to be the last thing, and their health is steadily declining, so trying to remove some of those barriers and I did some work with the local GP's and stuff, so kind of, responding when people need them, so I would imagine and I would like to think there is a huge impact on health." (Interview, Professional, 16)

Professionals both within and external to the Starting Point service provided numerous examples of case studies of people who had been supported by the service and were living independent, healthier lives. This included entrenched rough sleepers that external services struggled to support without the support of Starting Point:

"I'm sure I've got hundred [good stories] in a heartbeat but, here is one guy [...] who for years when I started doing this job was and I say this – back in the day, he would have been the town tramp. Right, you know, the older fella, liked a drink, was in town, err – you couldn't see how you're gonna change that and Starting Point did. So, they got him accommodation. They brought him food every day. They did whatever they had to do and to be fair [he] is still in that accommodation 4 years later. So, to me, that's a real success. That's one of the big things that you hear is Starting Point put people in its heart and it does have a massive impact.... actually I couldn't – I would never have never been able to give you the solution that's correct to house [him] at the time" (Interview, Professional, 3)

"Living in a property, staying in a property, she's coming in every Thursday at 1 o'clock, she's going to all her appointments, she's making her own doctor's appointments when she gets a letter; it is absolutely fantastic to see because sort of like last year, it, now she's, I don't even think she knew her name, she'd be singing, she'd be swearing, absolutely off the chart, so yeah that was another one for me, this is why we do our job because we see from somebody like that, that absolutely you can tell they need help and nobody's doing anything, you know maybe they're too chaotic or whatever, to then making people do something, the right channels or the wrong channels to see the success which is fantastic." (Interview, Professional, 16)

The positive impact of the service had led to other improved outcomes for people, such as strengthening relationships with family and friends:

"I've actually got, like, my family in my life again. You know, because I'm only, I'm like the only one what's, like, being a criminal. Because all my family, they all, they all work and that. They've all got jobs and houses and cars and all that. Whereas my sister, I fell out with my sister. I've not spoke to my sister since 2012. Since I went to jail...I think it was, it may be yesterday or the day before, I can't remember, but she's only just gone back and she come down with her husband to visit me for like a long weekend and it was just good to see her." (Interview, Person, 7)

Overall, it was clear that the Starting Point service was viewed very positively by people. When asked where they would be if they hadn't received support, several said they would be rough sleeping or engaging in risk taking behaviours which would have increased the likelihood of returning to rough sleeping:

“The Starting Point is a lot of people that help, like they are really good, like I would not, I think I'd be still on the streets if it wasn't for them. You know like they've done a lot for me at the minute, you know, it's nice.” (Interview, Person, 1)

“I'd probably did have been a massive chance of me reoffending... if I'd have been on the streets, no doubt I'd have reoffended. I'd have probably been flat out on drugs again. I'd probably be in jail by now. I really do.” (Interview, Person, 7)

“Probably be on the streets again” (Interview, Person, 9)

“It'd be either at my mum's but it's not very good there or I'd be on the streets because I'd have nowhere else to go.” (Interview, Person, 3)

Importantly, the support provided by Starting Point was contrasted to other services and the wider council, where people often felt that they were not listened to or their needs remained unmet. Interestingly, Persons differentiated the Starting Point service from mainstream council services, because of the service's commitment to understanding and tailoring support to their individual needs (explored further under 'Mechanisms of Success'):

“[...] I don't think you could [get this kind of support somewhere else]. Not not as much like this... Well I've never been supported like this before. [...] I feel like these have got a bit more time for people, and they care you know.” (Interview, Person, 1)

“And this is why as well we're, we're sort of in this building away from the corporate council, because people will say 'oh I can't stand the council they don't do nothing for me'. They don't realise that we are actually council and we don't, well we don't need to tell them.” (Interview, Professional, 1)

Overall, the service was considered by many people accessing the service and professionals as an essential lifeline and a key facilitator for them to move towards independence:

“I feel a lot better. See I've got the fight back in me now where a few years ago I was scared to go out the house to things. But now I've got the fight back in me. They're all backing me, do you know what I mean. I don't hate myself. I'm fighting for better, do you know what I mean.” (Interview, Person, 2)

“It is why I do this job, because you will never find that on a spreadsheet, you will never find that on a statistic, you know that real life moment where somebody is doing something that genuinely makes them happy, and makes them reconnect with their life, it's amazing and you get to do that a lot in Starting Point” (Interview, Professional, 14)

Improvement in Wellbeing Measured by the Outcome Star

Starting Point utilises the Homeless Outcomes Star as a way to monitor and understand individual support needs as part of routine practice. This is completed together with the individual and reviewed every 3 months, or if there is a significant change in circumstances. The Homeless Outcome Star consists of ten domains:

- Drug and Alcohol Use
- Emotional and Mental Health
- Managing money and Public Administration
- Managing tenancy and accommodation
- Meaningful use of time
- Motivation and taking responsibility
- Offending
- Physical health
- Self care and living skills
- Social Networks and Relationships

Each domain is scored separately out of 10; a higher score indicates that domain is less of an issue for someone. For example, take the Self-Care and Living Skills domain, if a person’s score increased from 2 to 5 it would indicate that they feel they feel their self-care and living skills had improved. The domains with the lower scores are the needs that Starting Point may want to prioritise supporting people with. The Homeless Outcomes Star is also used on an aggregate basis to measure impact in terms of the proportion of people that have maintained or felt they had experienced an improvement in each domain.

It is important to note that due to issues with accessing data, the Outcome Star data is analysed for people who are still being supported in the Starting Point service. To understand the impact of the service properly it would be beneficial to analyse the data for people who have been discharged from the service to understand what had changed between starting and being discharged from the service. This would highlight the impact on someone’s full journey from referral to discharge.

The data indicates that there was an increase in scores between the first-time people completed the Outcome Star, and the most recent time point in all of the domains but this increase was relatively small - often 0-2-0.5. There were three domains where the change was statistically significant. This means that we are confident that the measurement captured a genuine change rather than it being due to chance. The domains were: Emotional and Mental Health, Managing Accommodation and Tenancy, and Motivation and Taking Responsibility.

For most domains, the proportion of people who experienced an improvement was between a quarter and a third (see Table 3). For example, 30.9% of people reported feeling they had experienced an improvement in drug and alcohol misuse and 38.1% reported an improvement in motivation and taking responsibility. The improvement in a range of domains highlights the range of areas that Starting Point supports people with and is consistent with the learning from the qualitative interviews.

Alongside improvement, for each domain between 43-55% of people maintained their score. This indicates the preventative role that Starting Point has in terms of supporting people with complex needs to not deteriorate. About a quarter of people experienced deterioration in each domain. Further consideration is needed about why this deterioration has occurred - is it an area that Starting Point can support with or is it because of other aspects of people’s lives? The deterioration reflects how people’s journeys can face challenges and highlights the importance of using the Outcome Star as an active care planning tool rather than as a static outcome measure.

Reflecting on both the qualitative and qualitative data on the impact of the service, it was evident that whilst there may be relatively small changes on the outcome star, individuals viewed Starting Point as having a significant impact on their lives especially in terms of building trust in services and accessing support to meet their health, housing and income needs.

Table 3- Table of Homelessness Outcome Star Scores

Domain	1 st Score Mean	2 nd Score Mean	Statistical Significance- (P Value)*	Proportion of people that had an improvement	Proportion of people that stayed the same	Proportion of people that deteriorate
Drug and Alcohol Misuse	2.5	2.7	0.24- Any change may be due to chance rather than an observed improvement	30.9 (n=30/97)	47.4% (n=46/97)	21.6% (n=21/97)
Emotional and Mental Health	2.3	2.8	0.01- There appears an improvement in emotional and mental health which is not due to chance	33% (n=32/97)	48.5% (n=47/97)	18.6% (n=18/97)
Managing money and Public Administration	2.5	2.7	0.18- Any change may be due to chance rather than an observed improvement	29.9% (n=29/97)	50.5% (n=49/97)	19.6% (n=19/97)
Managing tenancy and accommodation	2.5	3	0.04- - There appears an improvement in how people feel they are managing their tenancy and accommodation which is not due to chance	28.9% (n=28/97)	51% (n=50/97)	19.6% (n=19/97)
Meaningful use of time	2	2.4	0.09- Any change may be due to chance rather than an observed improvement	28.9% (n=28/97)	53.6% (n=52/97)	17.5% (n=17/97)
Motivation and taking	2.4	2.9	0.02- There appears an improvement in	38.1% (n=37/97)	45.4% (n=44/97)	16.5% (n=16/97)

responsibility			how motivated people and how much they are taking responsibility for themselves which is not due to chance			
Offending	4.3	4.4	0.93- Any change may be due to chance rather than an observed improvement	28.9% (n=28/97)	46.4% (n=45/97)	24.7% (n=24/97)
Physical health	3.1	3.3	0.28- Any change may be due to chance rather than an observed improvement	27.8% (n=27/97)	47.4% (n=46/97)	24.7% (n=24/97)
Self care and living skills	3.1	3.3	0.42- Any change may be due to chance rather than an observed improvement	32% (n=31/97)	43.3% (n=42/97)	24.7% (n=24/97)
Social Networks and Relationships	2.3	2.5	0.47- Any change may be due to chance rather than an observed improvement.	22.7% (n=22/97)	54.6% (n=53/97)	22.7% (n=22/97)

*Statistical significance is known as the P Value. If the amount is less than 0.05 it indicates that we are confident that there is a genuine change between the start and latest score and that any change is not purely due to chance. So if one of the domains has a P Value of less than 0.05 then we are confident that in that domain, it appears that amongst the cohort there is an improvement in how people are coping with that specific issue such as managing their tenancy and accommodation.

Figure 3 - Mean Change in Homelessness Outcome Star

Figure 4- Number of people who experienced a change on the Homelessness Outcome Star

Impact of the Service on the Wider System

As well as benefits for individuals' accessing the service, professionals described the impact of the service on the wider system. Some felt the service reduced demand on overstretched health and public sector services:

"...It will reduce a massive amount of demand for us [in the police] ... It will reduce a massive amount of demand on the NHS, because he's putting even more demand on them than he is on us and at the moment things seem to be going in the positive direction. Whenever we're going out and the response team were arresting on a daily basis near enough, no matter what area, [...] that demand is reducing" (Interview, Professional, 9)

In particular, it was felt that the service was a "bridge" (Interview, Professional, 7) in provision for individuals with complex needs who did not fit within traditional services (explored further under mechanisms of success). Some professionals working within the Starting Point service felt that without the support, people would "slip through the cracks" (Interview, Professional, 7) of services. Another participant felt that the system would face significant challenges without the service. Providing wrap around support through the Starting Point alliance was seen as particularly beneficial:

"If we didn't have this alliance, and this grip around a cohort of people who are homeless or facing homeless with this level of complexity of need then the pull on other organisations and services would be significant. Erm, in terms of whether that be, um, you know presentations at A&E, you know, probation, involvement of our police colleagues, I think if we didn't have this approach we would see huge challenges in terms of well actually who would support these individuals who have this level of complexity in relation to their needs because actually traditional services and organisations, the approach that is within those organisations don't cater to the needs of these people so I think we'd have significant challenges from the system perspective" (Interview, Professional, 12)

Overall, it was clear the service has positive impacts on both the person and the system - through reducing demand and supporting better health and housing outcomes for individuals.

In the next section we move beyond impact to discuss the service's mechanisms of success – or what is working well, within the service.

Mechanisms of Success

The evaluation identified several key mechanisms for success of the Starting Point service, which facilitated positive outcomes. As well as supporting the development of the service the findings will have relevance to other services wishing to deliver integrated housing and health services to support the homeless population.

Advocacy, Flexibility and a Person-Centred Approach

A key mechanism of success greatly valued by people was the flexible, person-centred approach of the service which aimed to tailor support to individual needs. While the flexible approach presents

challenges (see 'Challenges' section), it was considered a central element of the Starting Point service which differentiates it from other traditional services.

An example of the flexible approach is that key workers can access the innovation fund which can be used to connect people with accommodation and support, as well as to purchase items which may support the prevention of homelessness. The fund is flexible and can be used in different ways depending on the person's needs. Several professionals were positive about this and described how they would have been unable to provide such support through their own services, although some challenges were also acknowledged (see 'Challenges' section):

“And they got pretty much, it seems to be from that perspective, open-ended credit cards that they can just keep going and buying things. I've seen that – I can see both sides you know, my [service] would say right, that's not how you should do some of the things cause if you took all that away, [name of person] would end up on the street, homeless 3 months later. And they're right, but actually I couldn't – I would have never been able to give you the solution that's correct to house [name of person] at the time. So, I mean there's been some real successes and ones I don't know. I do think there's been some real success” (Interview, Professional, 3)

The flexibility of the service, as well as a diverse workforce, allowed key workers to match skills and interests to people, which helped facilitate positive outcomes:

“I think we have all got our own sort of personalities and our own interest and areas, I think that we have had many times where one individual has been put with a certain case worker and it has completely not worked. So I think by having those individuals specialism and interests and sort of personalities within the team, we can sort of work out who fits best where and I think instead of, if you don't get on with somebody, its not going to work and you are never going to get anywhere and I think having that sort of freedom to say well that isn't working but it might work better with this person who knows more about this with this kind of personality.” (Interview, Professional, 7)

In addition, an important element of the key worker role was to provide advocacy for people both within the service and across the wider council. Advocating and being a “voice” for the cohort was considered a key aspect of the ethos of the service which was greatly valued by professionals both within and outside of the service:

“They are defiantly invaluable part of the fabric of services these days. That kind of, particularly being attached with local authority lends them a little bit of political weight to kind of keep, push services to get the best for people. The people will ultimately loose out and I would still do my job and I would still try my best but the people would most defiantly feel it, because they advocate, you know they push, they use political weight to make sure people and they hold people accountable essentially, you know, for, in fairness they don't have to do it too often, but sometimes people need a nudge in the right direction and just kind of remind them to step up and do their best for these people.” (Interview, Professional, 12)

For people, feeling like “someone cares” who was “fighting battles” on their behalf was extremely valued and contrasted to experiences with other services:

“Very, yeh [it is helpful]. Like my brain, it’s like, I don’t know. It’s not like an adult’s brain it’s like a kid’s brain, do you know what I mean so I can’t do, I don’t understand things. As much. Do you know what I mean? So it’s harder for me. Having [name of key worker] fighting my battles for me, getting through life, it’s a fight. Someone at the side of me who can do something for me. If I needed that [name of key worker] would, I’d see [name of key worker] and then if she can’t do it herself she’d put it on to like a person. But she does everything, she’s amazing.” (Interview, Person, 2)

“Well I think [name of key worker] is gonna sort it out for me. That’s why I like her ‘cos yeah she does everything. And sometimes it’s good you know. But yeah she’s, saw the Council and they weren’t happy that she said that I weren’t allowed... yeah she’s trying to be on my side with the social workers” (Interview, Person, 3)

For the service, the role of the key worker in coordinating housing and health services upheld Person’s rights by holding “organisations to account” which supported the completion of necessary support actions. Key to this was the service’s “empathetic approach”, which made people feel valued and listened to:

“Researcher: And what would you say is the best thing about Starting Point do you think? What’s helped the most?”

Person: Accommodation and being nice to me. Not being two-faced, as such...If I needed anything, I’d just come in and ask them. And try and sort it out for me. Yeah. No other’s nice like that. They seem really nice, yeah. They all work as a nice little team, even though they’ve got, you know, different people that they have to deal with” (Interview, Person, 6)

“There is all different things [why someone might be homeless] and when you start unpicking and unravelling it, you think no wonder you are at the place because some people they haven’t got that support as well from family or friends or they feel embarrassed to reach out for that support. So, for whatever reason it doesn’t matter what reason they are, we as a service will make them listen to, feel valued and hopefully feel safe and secure and make their life more positive and show them that they can do this.” (Interview, Professional, 17)

It was clear that service acted as a collective “voice”, which aimed remove stigma and improve understanding of the wider drivers of homelessness:

“Not just my individual job role, but as the team...we’re a voice. And sometimes people don’t want to hear it, and a professional challenge, people don’t always like and are receptive to, because they will see what they see and their sort of own biases etcetera what’s in front of them. But it’s our responsibility knowing what we know and how we are as a team, to open people’s eyes a little bit and sort of give an alternative and a different way of thinking...being compassionate because nobody is immune from that

situation. We've seen people, you know, people will think of homeless people and rough sleepers as oh well they're on drugs, they don't want to go to work, they're lazy, and all the sort of normal biases that come across. But we've seen people who have you know held down professional careers and have got families and just sort of hit a slippery pathway” (Interview, Professional, 1)

Overall, external professionals greatly valued Starting Point staff and acknowledged their caring approach and resilience when working with an extremely challenging person group. However, some challenges within the workforce were acknowledged (see ‘Challenges’ section):

“I have got massive respect for the team, I think that they are a cracking team, they work hard, and they work with some of the most difficult people, for very little reward in fairness, there is easier ways to make money, so they definitely do it because they care” (Interview, Professional, 15)

“Tomorrow might be the day that we get a breakthrough, and you know, get something sorted for them. So, just never say never and I think that’s what Starting Point does fantastically, never give up on anybody. They’re just amazing. They’re amazing team and they just work their damn hardest for everybody regardless of what they did yesterday... the dedication, skills, never giving up on anybody, always there” (Interview, Professional, 4)

Data from the observations of MDT meetings demonstrated the vast knowledge of staff both within and outside of the service of the Person group as well as the service’s empathic approach. It was clear that the local homelessness population was known to attendees, and the use of first names to describe people was common across all meetings. It was clear that the service discussed people not as a statistic but as a human with a need to be met. The relationships between key workers and people was evident:

“Use of first names to describe people, it was clear that the homelessness population was known to each attendee.” (Notes, Observation Meeting 2)

Housing and Health System Collaboration – Homelessness is Everyone’s Business

The Starting Point service was developed to support the integration of health, housing and social care services in response to major homelessness challenges in the borough. At the core of the model is the Starting Point Alliance, bringing together services under a signed agreement with the aim of working together to support those with multiple disadvantages and complex needs (including homelessness). By adopting a partnership model, the alliance acknowledges that addressing one issue in isolation is not enough to address the complex and interrelated causes of homelessness:

“So essentially the alliance is a strategic alliance with the premise that not one organisation has got the solution to meet the needs of the individuals who we are supporting so, the alliance is formed on the basis that actually we need to bring together organisations to work and support people who may, you know, be homeless or at risk of homelessness with a multitude of needs so that kind of complexity of needs so that kind of acknowledgment that this takes a range of services to be able to meet an individual’s needs” (Interview, Professional 12)

The Starting Point Alliance agreement is reviewed annually, and sets out the terms, roles, behaviours and understanding between services. This includes an agreement to support and work together to deliver shared responsibilities, attending monthly MDT meetings to discuss referrals, attending the Silver Group to discuss strategic priorities, data and performance, and to share relevant information and analysis which supports the delivery of the service.

“Maybe about a year into the project, there was this development of the Starting Point Alliance, so essentially what that is sort of a memorandum of understanding, agreement between partner agencies to provide a named contact or a specific service for those who are homeless, rough sleeping, and just a way of thinking differently to support the need of that cohort. So for example signed up to the alliance agreement we had [Organisation2 11:48], probation service, DWP, [Organisation3 11:54] which is the drug and alcohol service in [Place1 11:56], [Organisation1 11:57], all the sort of key players around that. So what that then means is that strategically all the leadership teams will come together to have a look at how they can support any sort of barriers, any sort of strategic plans where things can be amended or reviewed to sort of suit some of the challenges faced by homelessness and rough sleeping. More operationally what that does give us is access to individual workers, so they're either co-located with us and sit within the team, so for example erm DWP, we have a work coach that sits with us in our service and everyone knows her to be the Starting Point DWP worker.” (Interview, Professional, 1)

Consequently, the agreement sets out the following principles:

The Parties agree to adopt the following principles:

1. Collaborate and co-operate. Establish and engage in the governance structure to facilitate the delivery of the alliance objectives;
2. Be accountable. For all Parties to be held responsible for the delivery of the Complex Lives Partnership Model;
3. Be open. Communicate openly about major concerns, issues or opportunities relating to the Complex Lives Model;
4. Learn, develop and seek to optimise service delivery across Doncaster;
5. Work towards a shared vision;
6. Commit to common processes, protocols and other system inputs
7. Act in a timely manner and respond accordingly to requests for support; and
8. Act in good faith to support achievement of the objectives and compliance with these Alliance Principles.

Data from the observations and interviews demonstrated that a key role of Starting Point is also in coordinating actions across agencies and *“holding services to account”*. Within MDTs actions were regularly reviewed to ensure continued engagement from services:

“It creates that accountability for the agencies that are directly involved with an individual rather than sort of you know we could probably all talk till the

cows come home about certain individuals that we've got that have been around for a long time that are really entrenched. But for me, we kind of understand them people already. It's the new people that come in and the people that you know have had a decline where we need to make sure there's firm actions that are taken from that meeting and whose going to be accountable for taking that forwards." (Interview, Professional, 5)

"Actions within the meeting related to trying to locate people and to move on actions from previous meetings to ensure continued support, e.g., ringing organisations to see whether homelessness assessments have been made, making contact with services within other cities/towns to see if people have local connections or are back in Doncaster, again attendees know each people by name and know their circumstances (e.g. where they usually sleep, their social networks, support needs) (Notes, Observation Meeting 4)

Starting Point provided advocacy for people when other agencies were perceived as not offering the correct support or approach (e.g., by not adopting flexibility or empathy). The importance of multiagency partnership working in the delivery of support was evident across the meetings:

"[Person name] needs an urgent MDT and safeguarding review with mental health in attendance to formulate "a tight action plan around him and agreed commitment to professionals". The service is facing a lot of barriers due to lack of engagement from the Person but clearly he is not going to engage so we "need to go to him" - demonstrates the importance of wrap-around support. There is a "need to have these conversations at length and in detail with the right people around the table" to ensure the delivery of support actions" (Notes, Observation Meeting 2)

"[Name of housing provider] is now escalating the case to their manager after continuous lobbying from the senior manager at Starting Point. It was pointed out that the Person is being "failed by multiple agencies" – with a lack of referrals from required agencies e.g. social worker referral, OT referral. Person is not currently on the system. Support is currently "pretty poor" and needs escalation" (Notes, Observation Meeting 6)

Within the interviews practitioners described the benefits of the alliance for information sharing, shared ownership of tasks and feeling like a "collective", as well as being able to address the broad range of person needs simultaneously:

"The first benefit is, everyone has kind of access to the same information, the same insights, and the same data to then generate that shared understanding, but then that facilitates the conversations in terms of well, as a partnership, what do we collectively want to do together to address some of the challenges and what are our priorities, so I think the sharing of that information helps us to kind of provide that basis to then have those conversations because we're all working with the same insights and the same information, you've not just got one part of the system looking at their information and their data because it's a collective, as this is the system, as the alliance" (Interview, Professional, 12)

“...so if sometimes what they need is medication to get them stable enough, to be able to engage to get them into accommodation..., so what we would substitute medication to kind of them get them to a point where it unchains them from their addiction so they can spend time addressing issues like housing, the benefits, that kind of stuff, and again being part of the alliance, makes that so much easier.” (Interview, Professional, 14)

Some professionals described how they felt the alliance, and the Starting Point Silver Group more broadly, reduced the numbers of people falling between the cracks of services by facilitating effective referrals to different parts of the system. This in turn reduced demand:

“I think it is sometimes difficult isn't it where people, where people have got you know for example they fall between two stalls usually between substance misuse and mental health, I think that's, you know, that's often a challenge but by having mechanisms like the Starting Point Silver, where partner agencies come together we've got, you know, we've got escalation points where the service manager can bring things, but also partner agencies can bring anything that they need to highlight so I think as a whole it works” (Interview, Participant, 11)

“We can hopefully by working together, reduce those rough sleeper numbers because not only we're working with Starting Point, but we've got Probation Service, we've got the workers within Starting Point that work with Probation Service. Because what we're finding is people are getting released from the prison system, but they're getting released to no fixed abode, so they come straight out onto the street with no accommodation whatsoever. So, looking forward, by working with Starting Point, by working with Probation, by working with other agencies – hopefully that demand will actually reduce” (Interview, Professional, 9)

Coordinating actions and brokering relationships between agencies was also felt to support the prevention of homelessness, which was a key area of focus for the alliance. A move towards prevention through addressing the wider determinants of homelessness was felt to be essential to reduce demand.

“The view is that well we're trying to, from a prevention perspective, we're trying to prevent them then becoming on our cohort, so by the time they get to the point of needing us or rough sleeping it's - I say too late very loosely - but what are all the touchpoints that have happened? Especially in prison where they, you know, there's different services involved, and you know, from a social care, how many touchpoints have they had before they get to a point of needing us? Once they get to us it's not a solution it's almost like well, it's too late, they've they've dropped through that gap, which is what we want to try and prevent. So if we can get upstream of stuff by supporting and coordinating and brokering different relationships with different services, it's a bonus to everybody.” (Interview, Professional, 1)

Despite an interest in prevention and a clear understanding from Alliance members of its importance, a clear action plan to deliver prevention was not discussed regularly in meetings and it was not clear to the observer how this would be achieved (see recommendations). Since the evaluation it has

become clear that a delivery plan on prevention is in place (led by St Ledger), but it may be beneficial to revisit this plan, working closely with partners, to ensure an action plan to deliver on its aims is in place. The service’s impact on prevention is discussed further in the report in the challenges section.

The observation data from both the MDTs and Silver Group meetings demonstrated the effectiveness of the alliance. There was evidence of a collaborative and comfortable approach to data sharing from all partners and use of local data systems to provide information which supported several positive outcomes including the development of individualised support plans. The types of information regularly shared included:

“Previous addresses, current support needs, whether they are engaged in support, assessments in place including homelessness assessment status, whether prison leaver/engaged with probation services, mental and physical health service use and status, current location, drug/alcohol dependency, phone numbers and contact details for individuals” (Notes, Observation Meeting 3)

However, the majority of the information was provided by partners to the service, with data sharing from Starting Point to be limited (see ‘Challenges’ section). Data sharing within the MDTs resulted in a number of positive outcomes, including:

- **Locating missing individuals:**

The majority of data sharing within the MDTs is related to locating missing individuals to reduce disengagement the development and escalation of support plans:

“Actions within the meeting related to the location of missing people. Starting Point asked different organisations for information from their systems, e.g. [Housing provider] provided information on whether the person had presented at the homelessness services and whether an assessment had been made, whilst probation provided information on whether they had presented to their services and the actions following this. Providing this information meant that few people were unable to be located.” (Notes, Observation Meeting 7)

“Where someone can’t be located, Starting Point will use information from different organisations e.g [Name of housing provider] to see when the person last approached service, whether they have been placed in accommodation or have applied, and the Department of Work and Pensions to see if the person has applied for benefits” (Notes, Observation Meeting 4)

- **Triangulation of information to build a picture of Person needs and develop support plans:**

Data sharing enabled the bringing together of important information across different agencies (such as housing status and financial support) to build a picture of Person needs and provide wrap around support for the different drivers of homelessness:

“[Name of housing provider] accessed their internal system and confirmed a referral had been made to the private rented team and the Person had viewed and applied for a HMO. They are currently on the waiting list. An attendee from DWP viewed their system to confirm the Person was receiving benefits and is engaging with the job centre.” (Notes, Observation Meeting 1)

The partnership model and sharing of information ensures cases are reviewed during the meetings to ensure the maximum amount of support is being offered and that gaps in support can be addressed:

“Different agencies provided information from their systems to discuss the development of a wrap-around support plan. [Drug and alcohol service] provided information on whether the Person was engaging with support, whether they have a support worker, whether they have a prescription and if so what it is/dose. The police provided information on whether the Person has a warning marker, previous convictions, whether they have a police support worker assigned.” (Notes, Observation Meeting 8)

- **Coordination of support efforts:**

Services used information from their systems to discuss Person engagement with support services (e.g. via appointment attendance logs on local data systems). This supported the coordination of efforts to reduce people slipping between the cracks of services:

“Person missed their prescription pick up from [drug and alcohol service] so the support worker alongside a worker from the service will search for him tomorrow during outreach. The Person did not turn up to Changing Lives yesterday - need to locate them” (Notes, Observation Meeting 1)

- **Shared database between partners relating to safety and safeguarding:**

Services provided information related to safety and safeguarding to identify people that display behaviour that may put staff or others at risk:

“PVP – potentially violent persons database – can see people who show tendencies of being violent, this can be accessed by others and the team is encouraged to access this.” (Notes, Observation Meeting 1)

- **A focus on prevention:**

It was clear that multi-agency data sharing is key to preventative activities. For example, within the MDTs partners discuss upcoming evictions and releases from prison to support a preventative approach to homelessness:

“Eviction information from pending evictions not possible without engagement from housing associations. Shows importance of multidisciplinary alliance for prevention.” (Notes, Observation Meeting 7)

The decision of the Starting Point Alliance to focus on prison releases is a good example of preventative action. The partnership recognised the top 3 routes to the street (including prison releases) and wanted to understand what we can do differently (prevention opportunities). A round table event was held with reflection on 5 individuals who had been released NFA. A system wide plan was then agreed as part of this work.

Having Services and Embedded Workers “Under One Roof”

A key aspect of the Starting Point approach involved embedded workers from different housing and health organisations working within the service to provide wrap-around support to individuals. This helped address the wider determinants of homelessness. Professionals and people described several benefits of this approach. In particular, having dedicated embedded workers who were able to “problem solve” and advocate for people, such as by developing a network of professionals within

their organisations with direct contact details to streamline access to systems or providing equipment and support with IT, supported the removal of barriers:

“...for instance, Universal Credit is all online, absolutely everything is online, and these people don’t have any access to any type of equipment that – yes you can use public library, yes you can go into the [name of place] and use the free computers in there but in reality, that doesn’t work. If they haven’t – if they can’t set up an email address, if they don’t have a telephone number to verify that email address, it’s just a complete and utter waste of time and the effort and the frustration that it causes – you know, it’s tremendous and well, most people take basic IT as, you know, just a given that everyone can do it; but not everyone can, and they don’t have the access to do it. So, I found it really, really interesting and I found ways around that stayed within [name of organisation] guidelines but made it easy for the customer to be able to navigate...it is about problem solving, I have now gained experience and knowledge of how to help people by... you sort of learn to know who can support you with different benefits, gained experience of dealing with different departments, making contacts there and then being able to support our people by – not bypassing the system as such – but having contacts who are there to help and support you to get the best for people.” (Interview, Professional, 4)

Having multiple services delivering support from one organisation was considered particularly beneficial for people with complex needs who struggled to coordinate appointments. Overall, having “everything under one roof” was felt to support a move towards independence by bringing services directly to people:

“...everything under one roof is brilliant. So you don’t have to travel, do you know what I mean? I can’t say it because I go down there, but people on the streets don’t have to get this appointment, this appointment and like if I had two appointments instead if one were morning and one were night or one day or one were next day, do it in one session, do you know what I mean.” (Interview, Person, 2)

“When they are at a place and everything is there, we can get everything done. [...]. So I think having everything in one roof and making it as sort of easy as possible for them to access it, and they do when everything’s there, they do! But from going from point A to point Bb at a certain time on a different day, it doesn’t happen” (Interview, Professional, 16)

Reduce Barriers Accessing Mainstream Services

Professionals described several barriers that people faced accessing mainstream services, including completing online applications for benefits and housing, digital exclusion, a lack of equipment, not having contact details, and other vulnerabilities such as learning difficulties, as well as challenges in attending health appointments due to memory loss and difficulties in communication with health professionals (see ‘Challenges’ section). Despite these challenges, there were several examples of people accessing benefits and other forms of support through the service that they traditionally were unable to access:

“When you've been homeless for a lot of years, it's hard to remember. [Before Starting Point] well I never went to any [appointments]. I never did anything. [Starting Point] can get any appointment that you need, even dentists they can get you in there quicker.... She talks on my behalf, 'cos I let her, because I'd rather her speak, 'cos she knows, she can explain it better. 'Cos I'm dyslexic anyway so. And sometimes I don't remember things...because erm I think it would, I don't know, I think I wouldn't even talk if it weren't for them helping”. (Interview, Person, 1)

“They put your letters on computer, don't they? Yeah. And it saves it. See, I'm not computer literate, I'm just basic. So it confuses me, computers sometimes. I mean, if I weren't coming here, I'd have to go into a library, not library, I've got a library card anyway, so that helps with, you know, learning computers. But I'd have to go into a council and bid on their computers, that's what they've got, all those computers for them to. So, it's like little big steps” (Interview, Person, 4)

Building Trusted Relationships Over Time

Outcomes from the service take time and require consistent effort and determination from key workers to support the development of trusted relationships. Although this presented challenges (see ‘Challenges’ section), professionals provided several case studies of people who had previously disengaged with services but were now housed and living independently as a result of the continued support from the service. Key to this was the time taken from key workers and other professionals within the service to develop consistent, trusted relationships:

“So there's one particular individual who has been notoriously difficult to engage, he has been known to the service for years...He had been evicted from the hostels, evicted from the hotel, and he was quite content where he was. So because we was out on the streets, looking for him all the time, showing him that we was supporting him, I had given him an update every time I had seen him eventually because he learnt to trust me and he did come in for the support that day when he looked like he had hit rock bottom, he was then accommodated. He is now clean, off of substances, I believe him, I have never seen him looking so well. I think if we weren't here to support these individuals and build the trust with them then there would be a lot more deaths on the street, than what there are” Interview, Professional, 6)

Challenges to Service Delivery

Despite the Starting Point service providing positive outcomes, the evaluation highlighted some significant challenges both within the service and the wider system.

***“It's a constant battle”*: Mental Health Support Does Not Meet the Needs of Individuals with Complex Needs:**

A significant challenge discussed by several professionals was a lack of access to mental health support for people with multiple complex needs. One key issue is that mental health services will not provide support to people who have issues with substance misuse which creates significant barriers for the Starting Point cohort. For many professionals, this approach did not take into consideration the complex relationship between mental health and substance misuse:

“I don’t think there is enough understanding from sort of people who don’t work with people and do this job, I think they will see them and think, well you are a drug user and that’s the bottom line of it, whereas actually like I have said there is so much more underneath. [...] it’s not just physical health as well, its mental health, sort of like with mental health we have had numerous occasions of no, they are using drugs, we are not going to help them until they are clean, but then, well don’t we need to understand why are they using drugs?” (Interview, Professional, 5)

“I think because they put them in a box, they put them in this little box and think well you are smoking opiates and class A substance’s and whatever they are using and well they’ve caused your mental health issues. They don’t sort of see it as that they are using these substances to combat the trauma before” (Interview, Professional, 7)

“I’m sick of it, you know, maybe there is drugs in their system -laughs- maybe there is, but you know that’s not taking away what’s happening now and maybe actually people take drugs because they’re not very well... it’s difficult and absolutely needs acknowledging because I think every single one us, you know we’re trying to get mental health support and straight away it’s, ‘substance, well they tested positive for this two months ago’, that shouldn’t be the answer should it?” (Interview, Professional, 16)

On the other hand, providing mental health support to the cohort was identified as extremely challenging. A lack of access to a safe space to live and the coexistence of substance misuse meant that people were not *“in any form of stability to access psychological services”* (Interview, Professional, 7).

“I think when they’re on the streets it’s really hard to do any mental health work because they’ve got nowhere safe back to go to so and often their substance abuse is so high that that it wouldn’t be very meaningful anyway and you’d be distressing them in quite a large way and not got any other like so like alright so we’ve had our hour, off you go into world now. It doesn’t really work.” (Interview, Professional, 8)

For some, it was felt that mental health support related to medication or psychological therapies was not appropriate for much of the cohort and that the term *“mental health issues”* was used too frequently in the service when issues often relate to substance misuse:

“[...] ultimately they weren’t in a position for [mental health medication or psychological therapies]. I would rarely advocate for any of them to have prescription for medication, cos of the risk of death and none of them were really in any form of stability to access psychological services, so it felt like, everybody talks about mental health and ‘ah it’s his mental health, it’s his

mental health', realistically, it's very rare that it is their mental health"
(Interview, Professional, 7)

However, this is in conflict with quantitative data collected by the service which indicates two-thirds of people had a mental health diagnosis. 60% of people with a diagnosed mental health condition were on medication for it (59.6%, n=31/52). Just over half of people had received support from the primary care mental health teams (51.9%, n=27/52). A quarter of people with mental health conditions had or were receiving support from secondary mental health teams (25%, n=13/52). This indicates that a lot of people were not receiving support from specialist mental health teams raising the issue of who was supporting them to manage their mental health issues (see 'Recommendations').

Overall, it was felt by most professionals that mental health support for the cohort was extremely lacking, and that several changes were required at strategic level to better support homeless and other marginalised individuals.

"No, I don't think there'll ever be enough support. We've got very little mental health support. We did have some fabulous support, but they've both moved on. Obviously, we've advertised for loads of people to come into that role but it's not just about those two people. It's wider than that. You know, it's just very little support out there at all mental health wise" (Interview, Professional, 4)

"Yeah, I think it's, it's obviously their policies that's gotta change from up top, you know, I think they've got to have something in place to acknowledge, you know, substance users and mental health, rather than just say 'no, you're a substance, we can't work with you'. There needs to be that sort of niche in their service which there isn't." (Interview, Professional, 6)

"Complex people, complex system": Barriers in the Health System

Although there were several positive examples of the service improving access to services for people, significant barriers in accessing traditional services (particularly mental health) remain. Professionals described how it was very challenging for the cohort to access health appointments without the support of key workers due to vulnerabilities such as learning difficulties, brain injuries and memory loss and challenges in time keeping. Rigid appointment times which do not meet the needs of individuals with complex needs further exacerbate the issue. For many practitioners, *"health feels out of reach"* (Notes, Observation Meeting 16):

"I don't think we're getting enough support from GPs. I think it's very lacking – they don't understand. They're not willing to understand. You know, it's very difficult. They make everything – I feel like they make everything as difficult as possible. There's no support there to, you know, to help our people that don't have access to a telephone to phone at 8:00 in the morning. Everyone seems to have very rigid set rules that they're not willing to bend slightly for, you know, the most vulnerable people that can't use the normal services in the way that they want. There's lots of things out there that are extremely difficult for our cohort and our people to navigate." (Interview, Professional, 4)

“I think something that is hard is definitely around like GPs, and GPs and DWP are both very hard things around, for example lots of GPs now are doing this system where you do, do it online to get an appointment, you type in the whatever is wrong, whatever’s wrong, whatever the issue is and then they prioritise kind of appointments that way and they’re very strict on your appointment, this at this time, you turn up at this time, and that’s quite hard and part of the issue we have is quite, is like waiting rooms and having people sat in waiting rooms as they stress themselves out because they’re overwhelmed, they get bored and they’re like I’m not staying here anymore, I’m walking out, and it’s like I’ve got, at 8am, I’ve got on the system at 8am to get you this doctor’s appointment and now you’ve walked out and now you’ve DNA’d and they’ve put that down and there’s only so long before they kick you off the service and think that’s something that’s really head and not even just hard in terms of like practicality wise, but just very disheartening of like I’ve put all this work in and all you had to do was turn up and you’ve not managed to sit, you’ve not managed to stay” (Interview, Professional, 8).

“We need to ask is it the Person, the individual that's not engaging, or is it the service? And they're two different things. So if it's the service that's not engaging, well why? Do we need to sort of explore different ways of working, you know, for example some some areas of the service will have right if you don't come at 9 o'clock for your appointment then that's it, you can't come, we're not seeing you, you'll be struck off the books, three strikes and you're out. Then we would challenge that, say well hang on a minute, you know full well this person is rough sleeping in [Place5 30:48], you know ten miles out of [Place1 30:50], with no money, no telephone, no means of getting to you, we need to work differently with this person. So that sort of gives an example around that. And then we have some challenging people whereby they're not ready for that, they're not ready to be connected with that support, they're sort of, maybe in sort of a bit of self-destruct mode, they've fallen out with the systems, their trust in services has gone” (Interview, Professional, 1)

Indeed, people discussed the challenges of attending regular appointments. Difficulties in memory was cited as a particular challenge:

“Leaving, forgetting something yeh. I’ll be waiting for the bus, I could be having my phone out, put it down bus comes I’ll jump on bus, do you know what I mean? Yesterday I did it through train station.... Weeks and months, days and weeks just blend into one, do you know what I mean? So the time I just don’t know.” (Interview, Person, 4)

“While I was in prison I was going to the [name of place] because I've got issues with my memory. Like, I can remember stuff from years ago, but I can, I can do something. Say like if I'd done something yesterday, I probably won't remember it.” (Interview, Person, 7)

It was clear that several people had a historical mistrust in services which created challenges for person engagement (see next section). People frequently contrasted their positive experiences of Starting Point with other services (including the council) and national government.

“My partner had support. I just came with her because I could tell them. I didn’t have care. No-one cared for me.” (Interview, Person, 4)

“But the thing with it right, I’ve been homeless for 41 years you know what I mean. And I don’t know, why are they homeless for do you know what I mean? It’s the bloody government! they can’t do anything for the homeless. But the don’t give a fuck about us, they don’t give a fuck about the homeless do they?” (Interview, Person, 9)

However, professionals within the service and wider system acknowledged the challenges and efforts were made across the evaluation to make improvements to the health pathway. For example, a mental health and social worker were embedded within the service at the time of the interviews to support health/housing integration, although several challenges in embedding specialist roles into the service were identified (see ‘Challenges’ section). In addition, a psychologist was also introduced in April 2024 to support staff supervision and provide specialist psychological support including case formulation, reflective practice and training and development. Since the evaluation several efforts have been made to improve the mental health pathway, including commissioning work from an external consultancy to further understand the barriers and issues.

“I know they’ve introduced the psychologist who comes in once a month to do like case formulation and supervision, I think that is something that’s really positive and I think will really help” (Interview, Professional, 8)

Transitions – Vulnerable Transitions Points from Institutions – Hospital/Prison/Care

Recognising the challenges in their discharge pathway, the local hospital conducted a workshop focused on improving support for homeless individuals and sex workers. This was attended by a wider range of system partners including nurses, public health staff, hospital staff, VCS organisations and HDRC researchers. Several case studies were discussed which highlighted failings in the system and attendees reviewed and discussed these to find alternative solutions.

Several barriers in the health system were identified in the workshop such as stigma, long waiting times and a reluctance from people to wait without support, a lack of representation in the health service and poor communication between services. Challenges in the system such as short-term commissioning structures and an *“overreliance on numbers”* (Notes, Observation Meeting, 20) made showcasing the impact of services to health challenging. It was suggested that *“there needs to be recognition from the system that this may not be financially viable in the short term but will be in the long-term impacts from the work”* (Notes, Observation Meeting, 20).

Challenges and pressures in the health system were seen to be *“getting worse”* in a follow up meeting, where one participant described:

“[...] the current situation is not working and there is a lot of system wide challenges, so it is about identifying the quick wins which can implement which wouldn’t put pressure on one organisations, but could make a big difference to the system” (Notes, Observation Meeting 21)

Considering the challenges in the health system and to facilitate more effective collaboration between health and housing systems, it may be beneficial to convene MDT meetings around complex homelessness cases experiencing barriers in the health pathway. Attendees from Starting Point discussed the challenges in communication between agencies when patients are discharged to the street. There was a clear desire for Starting Point to work with other services and vice versa, but

capacity and constant “*firefighting*” created barriers. It was suggested MDTs could support better collaboration (see ‘Recommendations’).

Challenging Cohort and Service Disengagement

The evaluation outlines that the road to recovery for Starting Point Persons can be nonlinear and complex, with various challenges contributing to people’s relapse, disengagement from the service, or return to the street. This included relapse into drug-taking, maintaining poor relationships, the experience of stigma, barriers to support systems and systemic mistrust.

“Which has done my head in because I was doing really well in [Place2 02:36]. I was staying off the drugs and that, and sticking to my medication, and then every, erm sometimes when I see him I’ll have drugs again so it’s just bad everything but you know. And it’s got no good in the end and this is why I’m saying I don’t want to be in [name of place] I need to be away.” (Interview, Person, 1)

Starting Point staff described several Persons who continuously disengaged with the service despite sustained effort from key workers. Interviews with staff and meeting observations highlight the emotional toll and frustration of this for staff, who sometimes felt their efforts went unnoticed by the cohort (see ‘Workforce’ section):

“And although we’ve got fantastic support from the support workers, often they’re banging their heads on the brick wall and it’s – It’s really frustrating and – and sometimes the people say well, you don’t do anything for me but they don’t see that you spent 10 hours, you know, trying to contact the GP; or 20 hours trying to get through to mental health services to support them and it’s a waste of time trying to talk to anyone cause they just don’t want to know. So, no. There’s not enough support at all I don’t think.” (Interview, Professional, 4)

“Trying to find her a property, possibly in the private rented. It is becoming really difficult to know what the Person wants and they are very aggressive when approached on the street. Person says that the council are not helping her. This perhaps suggests that she is not suitable for an accommodation placement” (Notes, Observation Meeting 2)

“Concerns over Person as their physical and mental health is deteriorating. They desire supported accommodation but are known for continuously refusing this. Looking to escalate the support and safeguarding of this individual.” (Notes, Observation Meeting 3)

“No quick fix”: Difficulties Discharging People from the Service

Linked to the above, it was clear from the interviews and observation data that the Starting Point service was a “*longer term approach*” which requires consistent effort to maintain people’s engagement.

The complex nature of the Person’s backgrounds, alongside barriers within the system, meant that there was “*no quick fix*” to support people out of homelessness. It was acknowledged that building trusted relationships takes time and consistent effort, particularly when people have had historical mistrust in services. This meant that some people, particularly entrenched rough sleepers, received

support from the service for a long period of time. The mean length of time of support was just over 4 years. Just over half of people had been supported by the service for over 5 years (55.7%, n=54/97), the longest-supported person currently in the cohort had been in service for over 7 years.

“I think there’s multiple issues [...] we’ve got individuals that you know are in difficult relationships. Abusive relationships, they’ve suffered childhood trauma. That has a big impact and a knock-on effect to them then going on to use substances, to offending. People that have lost every option that they’ve got in terms of accommodation. They’ve been in every supported housing that we’ve got available to us in Doncaster and its ended badly because the right support’s not been in place, so they return back to rough sleeping. You’ve got issues with physical health. You’ve got obviously the mental health and then you know that self-neglect. Like they don’t think they’re important, so they don’t look after themselves. So again, that’s something that has to be built a long time which is why you know we end up involved with people for you know long periods of time because it’s hard to build a relationship with people. And it’s hard to rebuild that trust when they feel like you know they’ve been let down and they’ve had their fingers burned several times, so it’s difficult. I think there’s no quick fix with the individuals that we support, especially if you’ve got a multitude of different support needs.” (Interview, Professional, 5)

“I mean there’s people on my caseload that have been known to our services that have been rough sleeping and then this sort of cycle for years and years and years and years and years, and it just keeps going round in a circle. What I’ve seen and the ones that I’ve had positive sort of discharges with are the ones that have not been particularly homeless very long.” (Interview, Professional, 16)

Although the need for longer term support for some individuals was acknowledged by some professionals, there was a perception that this was not shared across the wider council. Some felt that there was a view that outcomes needed to happen more quickly, with a focus on housing people as quickly as possible without a consideration for the wider determinants of homelessness. This was frustrating for some practitioners:

“I mean there’s some where we have quick turnarounds and quick wins as we call them in terms of, you know, we can get them connected with services and it is just that prevention stuff. But when someone’s entrenched in a way of living, in a mindset, not trusting of service, excluded from services, sort of, you know, have difficulty getting involved and being accepted, you know, then the past trauma and all that sort of stuff, people see a problem and it antisocial behaviour and well why can’t... I mean I’ve heard it myself, people say in the city centre well if they just got a job. Oh right OK well why didn’t we think of that? Now, oh, there’s plenty of empty properties in why can’t they just go into there?” (Interview, Professional, 11)

The long-term support required for some people meant that it can be difficult to discharge people from the service. In addition, the intense nature of support and the personal responsibility felt by key workers meant that it was sometimes difficult “to let go of people”. Some professionals felt that this

resulted in key workers working with people longer than required, which did not always result in a move toward independence:

“I think what we are as a service a bit rubbish at for want of a better phrase is we will hold, hold on to cases and actually we need to remember that what we're trying to do is get people to a place of independence where if they need services, they go to the mainstream services, and I think we often feel like if we let people go, and they're not connecting with those services, it's almost as if we're failing them. So sometimes we're a bit of a make a rod for our own back if you like, because you know, we want people, that's that the aim, to get people to be more independent and access services, have better quality of life” (Interview, Professional, 11)

In addition, the high risk, complexity of support and continued disengagement of some people added further challenges. When people are high risk but not actively engaged with the service it is very difficult to discharge them and exacerbates the feelings of personal responsibility felt by key workers. This raises the question of at what point should support be removed if people continue to disengage:

“It's something that I have been trying to get my head around as well, because I know that disengagement is a big problem and that's not surprising considering the cohort and some people have to keep pushing and pushing and pushing, to get engagement with people and in my head, I think at what point do you think, this person just isn't ready, they are not ready engage and you are putting your head and soul into something when they just are not there....the worker I have done a lot of work with as far as I am concerned she walks on water, she's brilliant, just the breadth of stuff, social care and stuff, she had to pick all that up and she's already kind of talked about, how do Starting Point exit from this?” (Interview, Professional, 4)

“It's difficult, it really, really is difficult. I mean I think it's something that we're now trying to put as a team but I know there is them people there's, I've got one that's been on the caseload forever; her engagement is the bare minimum, she does absolutely nothing, I have to go to her house every week, but substance misuse is that high, she's got self-neglect, she doesn't look after herself, there is, you know and I've had to manage her under a scenario level 3 you know because her chances of death are quite high. So even though she's not particularly doing anything for herself, there's not a great deal I can do because, when I went to see her yesterday, we'd said right, come up to [name of service], you know, you're constantly repeating yourself and it doesn't, it's the same thing, but I can't discharge her because of the high risk.” (Interview, Professional, 6)

Some professionals who had closely worked with the service since its inception felt that its remit had changed over time to support more people with varied needs, rather than concentrating on the most complex. This was felt to have become too “unwieldy” for one professional and had implications for capacity and workload:

“It was definitely doing something different [when it started]. My understanding of Starting Point when it was starting was it would be a fairly small cohort of the most intense people and then you'd be working intensely

with those people, now that doesn't mean every day. Mine was more of that old school when the person needed the support, you're able to chop and change, you've got a small case load and you're able to really put the support where it's needed at different times. Err, it very quickly grew into something – I felt looking in on it – was quite unwieldy and fairly unmanageable. You know you had a cohort of a hundred and something people. We can't – you can't just keep going, well that person's here – there's everybody, you know. So, it became quite unwieldy.” (Interview, Professional, 3)

Some practitioners made suggestions to support the discharge or step-down process, including preplanning for possible discharge by introducing new members of staff in new areas of the service. It was acknowledged that “*discharge was tough*” and required a “*conscious step back*” from key workers to manage the transition (Professional, 5). Some professionals felt building independence and teaching new skills to manage everyday life (such as cooking skills and managing finances), alongside encouragement to attend appointments independently, were key to successful discharge. However, although the flexibility of the service was seen as a positive, some felt that the structure of the service was not adequately “*preparing people for normal services*”. One practitioner suggested that flexible support should remain until people are housed, and at that point should move towards encouraging more independence:

“I don't think we're really preparing them for normal services...I think it's hard because normal health or social work is so structured and so rigid, but eventually the idea of Starting Point is to put them into normal services and I don't think that's really happening in the way it's currently structured... if that case worker's been really consistent with people and really trying, and I think you build that relationship and that trust with the whole of Starting Point rather than like just you're one case worker and then that will transfer onto health services you know, we'll support you to your first appointment, we'll take you and then eventually they would build up on their own of okay so today you can come on your own and see what happens” (Interview, Professional, 8)

The service acknowledged the limited nature of the support offer once people were housed within some of the MDT meetings, and the need for longer term support for some people:

“It was acknowledged for this individual that it may not be Starting Point that provide support [when depending on if he is housed but the Person clearly requires long term support from somewhere, so there is a need to explore options.” (Notes, Observation Meeting 1)

Challenges in Multidisciplinary Working

Although there were clear benefits to the system collaboration that had been developed within the service, several challenges in multidisciplinary working emerged from the evaluation. One such challenge was a perceived duplication of roles within some areas of work such as outreach. Related to this, one professional felt that the work of Starting Point was much more visible and that as a service they got praise when an outcome may have occurred because of the input of a number of services. There is a need to consider how to demonstrate the impact of Starting Point in partnership with other services.

“I think for me the main bit is duplication and clarity of roles cause I think for certain others – city centre management sometimes look in and they’ll be sort of they clump everybody together, but you’re kind of doing very different things but all they’ll see is well [name of team]” (Interview, Professional, 3)

Although there was some evidence of duplication of roles, some professionals also discussed differences in the aims and objectives between Starting Point and other services which sometimes made operational delivery challenging:

“I think there’s challenges from an operational service delivery perspective, obviously there’s a lot of demand, front door demand which [name of housing provider] experience on a daily basis, erm, from a wider homelessness perspective and you know Starting Point, we’re talking about a very specific cohort of people, obviously [name of homelessness service] is you know, far reaching, it affects families, it’s not just about single homeless and people you know experiencing rough sleeping, it’s far wider than that, so I think you know operationally, you know, there is a bit of butting of heads I think at times would be fair” (Interview, Professional, 11)

In addition, although the information sharing across the Alliance was generally praised and resulted in several positive outcomes (see ‘Mechanisms of Success’ section), some felt that this was sometimes “one sided” (Interview, Participant, 3). Indeed, observations of some of the MDT meetings indicated that information sharing relating to person support needs (e.g. whether people had engaged with services, were currently taking medication etc) were often provided by support agencies to Starting Point. However, this is a reflection of the type of support provided by the service, which aims to broker relationships between services rather than providing support. It may be useful for the service to consider whether it holds useful information which could be provided to external support agencies.

In addition, some practitioners questioned the continued buy-in from services to the alliance and felt that the Silver Group could be better attended by some services. Indeed, observation of the MDTs and Silver Group meetings showed inconsistent attendance from health partners, although this improved across the lifetime of the evaluation with attendance from representatives from the local hospital and a GP becoming more common. The lack of engagement from health partners was acknowledged in several Silver Group meetings and caused challenges in the progression of support pathways. Some professionals in the interviews suggested that a relaunch of the roles, remit and responsibilities of the group may be beneficial to ensure continued buy in (see ‘Recommendations’). Interestingly, the research team held two workshops to present the evaluation findings and further refine the recommendations to both system leaders and the operational team in September 2025. Despite each member of the alliance being invited and most accepting the invitation, only a small number of the partner organisations attended, with low attendance from health partners.

“I think in terms of what could improve...I think that wider alliance I think it got away from us a little bit so we did used to have a series of meetings where quite senior representation from some of the alliance members and we used to meet regularly, it was very structured in terms of the agenda and again like a golden thread but it was a really good way of keeping people sited, I think recently, the silver group that they refer to the sort of strategic management group, I think sometimes the attendance isn't great from the alliance members and I think that sometimes, some of the challenges that we face are with some partners who either again changing personnel or lost sight

of you know what the service is about...again with COVID, it did mean that a lot of agencies retracted into their own organisations and because they did used to colocated, I think some of the co-location has gone a little bit and I think the minute that people aren't sat physically together, it sometimes makes it feel a little bit one step removed so I think there's certainly something about rejuggling our assets around that broader alliance, you know, in terms of value for those meetings and certainly in terms of how we can work together in a more stronger way" (Interview, Professional, 10)

As well as seeking better attendance from those already involved in the alliance, it was felt that the Starting Point silver group and the service more widely would benefit from more involvement from new support services. As discussed earlier in the report, several professionals felt engagement with health services, such as GPs and dentists, to be lacking:

"I think improvement wise; we need – we need more support services to come and work with us absolutely desperately. You know, the more people that are in the building supporting people, the better service that we can provide and hopefully get better outcomes." (Interview, Professional, 15)

Ensuring buy-in at the organisational level, not just the individual, was also cited as a key challenge. This was seen as a key role for the Silver Group. Considering the current membership of the group, it may be useful for the service to target individuals working at a strategic level to ensure the translation of the work of Starting Point into tangible changes to policy and practice (see 'Recommendations')

"I think there's something just about how we are clear and have got a consistent approach the best way to make sure that this multiagency approach can service that delivery model and is it always about an individual or is it more about...and again I suppose that comes back to, if it's an individual sometimes it's as successful as that individual buys into it, whereas if you can get it at an organisational level, then it doesn't matter who's here, it is something that that organisation recognises and values and therefore it leads into so I think there's something about that that maybe is a challenge sometimes." (Interview, Professional, 10)

Acknowledging the challenges, some professionals made suggestions to improve joint working practices between organisations, such as bringing partners together for joint meetings to discuss more complex cases, as well as a half day away day:

"I think we definitely need to get something in place to have a joint meeting whether that's half day, full day to -- because we're working from two different buildings as well, you don't always know that other person end of the phone you know the name -- but if we can personalise it a little bit, it makes it easier because again I think took over just after Covid, so were using phone calls, you didn't get to have that sort of personal relationship with -- with them. So, whereas now, cause we can see each other; [Name 3, 15:38] can come up. I don't think it'd potentially need to be another MDT. But if we could have something where we discussed the complex cases, the ones where they have been issues in the past, maybe a bit of sort of action learning. So, this is a case that's riled my member of staff up, let's have a look at it, let's break it down together (Interview, Professional, 2)

Inconsistent Understanding of Starting Point Remit

Although the flexibility of the service was greatly valued by people and several services, it was acknowledged that it created some inconsistencies in service delivery. Whilst interviewees within the service were clear on the aims and remit of Starting Point, this was not consistent across all staff groups or external services. Despite investment from the service to develop levels of support and to launch this externally to partners, there was still some confusion on the remit and differences between each level:

“I can’t work out, whose who, what are the roles, I still cannot work it out...it is very confusing. I don’t know what the differences are in them, I know they have got different roles. They swop jobs as well, so it’s really hard to keep up with whose who and what’s what and what job role, I really don’t know, I really really don’t know. I know who I phone, and I know who would help me, if I needed it and who I help and who their people are. I think its somewhere, it’s been forgotten why they are there, but its about people, its not about them at all, and I think a lot more could be done for the people out there, that is not being done and there doesn’t seem to be any clear pathways or processes at all.” (Interview, Professional, 15)

“I think sometimes at Starting Point that can get muddled, because you’ve got so many different elements to that team, which is great in one part, but in another it could really get messy - and I think that clarity’s missing at times.” (Interview, Professional, 5)

In addition, there appeared to be some confusion over the differences between Housing First, SHAP and other MEME workers, and why people needed to change case workers depending on the different intervention. Some felt this created confusion and instability for people:

“I think they [have clarity on the levels] within the service, but I think they’ve overcomplicated it... I personally, would struggle to see where the role of a MEAM is needed. Personally, because, especially now you have Housing First, so then you have a Housing First MEAM... Basically a Housing First MEAM is the same as a MEAM, just for Housing First people. So it wouldn’t be seen as a journey I think, it’s not like they’re deescalating down to support workers or anything like that. I think, to me really, across the board they’re all similar in what they should be offering. They’ve just complicated it and it’s given some people a little bit more... of not self-importance, you know if you said to some of them, they’d get quite offended about being labelled as a support worker but that’s the same for us, I mean do you know I would never turn round and say oh I’m not doing that, that’s not my role I’m [name of job role]. Like, you just do what needs to be done for the best outcome for the Person” (Interview, Professional, 13)

“...so with [Housing First] that doesn’t make any sense to me as to why we’re transferring them over at the most instable period as well where they’re moving into an accommodation and learning to live on their own and we’re pulling that consistent support out and putting a new person in. So, I don’t think that works well but I think, for me, in all honesty, I don’t see a role for the MEAMs. I think outreach should be, if they upped their game, outreach

should then hold a small caseload of the entrenched rough sleepers and do the work on the street with them. Then once they start to engage and they kind of pick up some speed along their journey, transfer to a navigator, to get them into and support them with housing applications and things like that, or from outreach into Housing First and SHAP, and then you, instead of them going through all these different channels they've gone straight from consistent support on the street to the consistent support in accommodation." (Interview, Professional, 8)

Furthermore, some professionals noted differing views on the outreach role and the amount of time required in the office versus providing on street support. Some professionals felt that outreach workers spent too much time in the office which went against the remit of the service. In addition, some individuals mentioned a lack of clarity between outreach and key worker roles, particularly concerning who was responsible for providing on-street support:

"There's a lot of meetings that happen, I think that takes up a lot of time, and then case workers do the same where if they were housed they go and visit them but if they're on the streets they don't and there's kind of this disconnect between should it be the case workers going out to find them or should it be the outreach going out to find them and bringing them to Starting Point to see the case workers. But, that, that's not happening and case workers going out to find them isn't really happening so it means they're booking appointments but they don't turn up so they're like okay, that's done then, we're not, we're not doing anymore" (Interview, Professional 7)

"...but to me the welfare checks are basically waking them up to make sure they're alive and then moving on...I just think, where's the compassion? Like where is the time, how do we have an outreach team who are not out on the street for the whole shift?" (Interview, Professional, 13)

Some professionals also discussed inconsistencies in the use of the physical space. Whilst some practitioners described how people were welcome to use the Starting Point service space when they wanted, others felt this had become too "regimented" with people having to wait outside to be buzzed in for specific appointments only. For some professionals this went against the flexible and supportive remit of the service:

"I think there's just been a bit of disconnect between what the service, what different people think the service should look like because for example there was also...in, my personal opinion is that they're, I mean it's hard because I don't know how you would man it safely and have enough staff around, but my personal opinion would be that people can come in for a drink at any time of the day, they can come in to use the toilet, they can kind of use the space as a social space when it's cold outside, because I think it'd be helpful for people to grab them and be like great, you're here, let's do this work. Whereas, what happens is, it becomes very like strict and regimented of well we can't have too many people in the building so if they're in the building, they have to be, their case worker, they have to be doing work with their case worker, they can't just come in, they can't come in to use the toilet, they have to wait outside and wait for the case worker to collect them from outside and be buzzed in by reception, stuff like this, and I think it just becomes very

regimented as a service and like kind of like other services which I don't think is what it's meant for." (Interview, Professional, 8)

"...that social space shouldn't be called a social space because it's not social at all, nobody goes in there...I feel like people should be able to access a toilet if they need it and they should be able to access a drink and some snacks if they need it, and I think it's quite disgusting that we make people wait outside in the rain and just reinforces that they're not worth, yeah they're not worth anything." (Interview, Professional, 13)

Several professionals felt that the support received depended heavily on the individual support worker and their approach which created inconsistencies across the service and meant that some people were not receiving the same levels of support. Whilst the flexibility of the service to adapt to individual need is a key mechanism of success of the service, the findings indicate that it may be beneficial to introduce some baseline expectations within each level of support (see 'Recommendations'):

"I think it is lack of consistency, I think it depends which worker it is, how they work, whether they would want to do that. I am not quite sure, because some people seem to do above and beyond, same as me, and would go that extra mile to help their person and then other people don't seem to care" (Interview, Professional, 15)

Others described a misunderstanding of the remit of the service from external agencies. There was a misconception among some that Starting Point was a provider of housing and health services, whereas its function was to connect people with existing health and housing services. Some felt that there was an overreliance on Starting Point to provide support for complex cases, with an expectation the service "will do everything". Again, this reinforces the issue that some services lack understanding of the remit of Starting Point and adds further weight to the need for further information sharing to external partners (see 'Recommendations').

"So a lot of the time we've knocked people back and said well actually the only unmet support need that you're identifying is that they need somewhere to live. We're not the housing provider, that needs to be [name of organisation]. We're the support provider, now if you're saying there's a gap in the support that we can pull together, that's where we would come in" (Interview, Professional, 1)

"... we get a lot of, its alright Starting Point is involved, we'll back off. We get a lot of that off social care, which is naughty. Safeguarding, when I have submitted lots of safeguarding, it's like well what do you want us to do, and I'm like well I have submitted it because it's a safeguarding issues, I want you to give me some specialist advice or do something and getting them to be accountable as well because they think its alright Starting Point will do everything. We do, do a lot of things but we can't be everything to everybody" (Interview, Professional, 17)

"If we are trying to create accountability and a multi-disciplinary team around an individual then we need to tighten up the way that we are having these discussions and working out who's going to pick what up because we can't essentially, as much as we'd love to, be everything to everybody. You know and we're not mental health workers. We are not social workers. We

are not drug and alcohol workers. We are not nurses. We are not doctors. We are there to sort of walk side by side with that individual while they're on the journey that they're on and try and match them up with these professionals that have been identified as needing to be involved.” (Interview, Professional, 5)

Although Starting Point has invested in developing the service specification and communicating this to partners, the findings indicate that further information sharing would be beneficial to ensure all agencies understand the remit and ethos of the service, including the support provided and differences between intervention levels (see ‘Recommendations’).

“Yeah I think [more clarity] would be useful so, and I think to even just to the people themselves, like this is kind of the expectation of what your role should look like because I think people don't really know what they're meant to be doing. And like all the roles kind of get like mixed together.... I think maybe just clarity across the whole team of what is the purpose of the team, what do they want to achieve, because I do think people have different ideas around how they want the service to look” (Interview, Professional, 8)

Reactive Versus Preventative Service?

Data from the observations of both the MDTs as well as strategic level meetings show that the levels of new rough sleepers are reducing and therefore the service is having a positive impact on primary prevention (for example, as of September 2024 there were 12% new rough sleepers compared to 29% per cent nearest neighbour and 25% regionally - Notes, Observation Meeting 12). However, a notable challenge discussed in several meetings were the high numbers of people returning to rough sleeping (65% returning to rough sleeping, compared to 33% nationally - Notes, Observation Meeting 12).

For several practitioners this is *“Doncaster’s most significant pressure”* (Notes, Observation Meeting 12) and a large amount of resource and time is used to support 17 rough sleepers who were known as frequent returners to the service. As such, it was acknowledged across the meetings that *“early intervention and prevention need to improve”* (Notes, Observation Meeting, 16) and more work was required to move from *“a reactive support service to a proactive service”* (Interview, Professional, 1). In addition, despite an interest in prevention and a clear understanding from Alliance members of its importance, a clear action plan to deliver prevention was not discussed regularly in meetings and it was not clear to the observer how this would be achieved (see ‘Recommendations’).

Since completing the evaluation, it has become clear that a prevention plan has been developed (led by St Ledger), but it may be beneficial revisit this, working closely with partners, to ensure an action plan to deliver on its aims is in place to drive change forward. This could include undertaking a ‘deep dive’ to better understand the needs and barriers facing the 17 entrenched rough sleepers and how support can be better tailored to their needs. The action plan should align with wider work being undertaken around prevention within the council.

Changing Support Workers

Within the Starting Point model people transition through different levels of support and are assigned key workers depending on which intervention they are receiving. This meant that some people, particularly those who had been with the service for a long time, had moved key workers several times. Some people described how they found this disruptive and confusing, and made it difficult to build trusted relationships:

“But I had loads of workers, I've had loads of different Starting Point workers... like I've had about eight probably....I hate it, because I hate getting new workers that I don't know. 'Cos erm I'd rather just keep one, 'cos I don't, you know. I don't seem to get along with a lot, like with just anyone, do you know what I mean? I don't know. I've always been like that. Like sometimes I don't like talking to them about anything do you know what I mean? It's just easier [to have one person]. Like they know, you're not having to explain yourself that many times, they know” (Interview, Person, 1)

“Well, I was telling [first key worker] she moved me on to [second key worker] who's left now, she left last week, so I hardly got to know her.... I don't like it. Because I got used to [name of key worker] and I only had [second key worker] until recently, until the last six months. I've been messing about, going backwards and forwards, and wanting to know who my support worker is” (Interview, Person, 3)

Some professionals recognised the negative impact of changing support workers, and felt that this was detrimental both to staff and people:

“How I feel, you get a person now, you're doing what needs to be done, you're getting it done, they're going to somebody else, it's not good - whereas before, you'd get your person and you'd sort of see them all the way through to, and you'd be striving for that so they got, do you know what I mean, to the other end, and I just don't think it's good, I don't think it's good for us as staff when they're changing workers and it's certainly not good for people because you're working on building that trust, that personality, that sort of you know, friend, not friends, friendly but not, I'm not you know that sort of thing and they've told you things that they've not told other people and then they see that you're abandoning them again and they've got to start all over again, so I think it has a really negative impact” (Interview, Professional, 16)

Operational and Political Context: Homelessness Stigma and Attitudes Across Wider Council

Some professionals across the interviews and observation data were concerned about attitudes to homelessness across wider council services. Linked to the section above, some professionals felt that there was a lack of understanding around how long it takes to support people, a preoccupation with quantitative data and the numbers of people on the streets rather than understanding lived experience, and that the priority needed to be housing people without an appreciation of the wider drivers of homelessness. Changing attitudes and removing stigma across the council was considered a key priority for the Starting Point Alliance:

“There might be antisocial behaviour in the city centre, and sometimes we get then a label attached to individuals in the city centre causing antisocial behaviour can be, er, inappropriately attached to rough sleepers and when we kinda unpick that actually it's not rough sleepers that are causing that antisocial behaviour, um, and so we're really keen to address and challenge, the kind of stigma around rough sleeping and to make sure, where there is any, assumptions made, around rough sleepers... Across the council [it is a challenge]. So, I think it's more of a council wide issue that I would say we're

really keen, to do as a partnership to be careful of that kinda language, and those stereotypical assumptions around homelessness people that we're quite keen that we continue to do that. Cos we've still got that challenge."
(Interview, Professional, 12)

Indeed, discussions in some of the observations, particularly meetings at the strategic level, were primarily concerned with numbers of those on the street. Evidencing the impact of the service to decision makers to make the case of the service (and for wider preventative services) was acknowledged to be extremely challenging due to a preoccupation with the need to reduce rough sleeper numbers and to assertion the cost savings of the service:

"Well one of the, one of the propositions we put forward and it, it's a bit like prevention, you know, the argument for prevention rather than the more acute end of any kind of service is that how do you quantify or demonstrate the value of something you prevented happening, it, if you look at some of the early documentation that provided the business case for Complex Lives, it was dedicated on saying do you realise that a rough sleeper will typically experience X, Y and Z and maybe contact with criminal justice service, blah blah blah, erm, and it costs as a, you know, as a system this but if we invested this, you could save so there was certainly a financial erm motivation for doing it, whether or not there's any way of keeping track on, you know, being able to monetise the fact that 3 people either were sleeping rough for a very brief period and now they're in some form of supported accommodation I don't know, but there was certainly an economic benefit put forward because unfortunately we operate in a world don't we where you know it, when budgets are tight and it's public sector you need to be able to demonstrate the value of doing something," (Interview, Professional, 10)

In addition, although the Starting Point Silver Group acknowledged the importance of taking a holistic approach which takes into consideration the wider drivers of homelessness, it was clear this was not shared across all council teams. For example, in a strategic level meeting there was evidence of a greater desire for more integrated working between Adult Social Care and the service to ensure that care act assessments were undertaken with risk rough sleepers, which did not appear to be consistently prioritised:

"Assessments by social care are critical – 7 dimensions, 2 are housing e.g. can they safely maintain a tenancy. Broader social care assessment of needs is potentially required for the 17 people within the service who are entrenched rough sleepers. It was acknowledged that there is a need to move away from blaming the individual, so "it's more about the system" and "the system's response to challenge". Need to be looking at the social care need aspect not just housing. It was agreed this would be taken to the next Silver Group to "get the system to respond to this" - in Doncaster there is a need to look at the assessment of needs and knowledge of the individual to understand what accommodation is needed and how the system can work backwards to achieve that. It was suggested that the partnership is asked to agree to care assessments for all 17 of the entrenched rough sleepers" (Notes, Observation Meeting 12)

The need to work more closely with social work was discussed in other meetings. Given the social care challenges of the cohort and potential issues in joint working, it may be beneficial to consider introducing an embedded worker who is contracted with the social care team. In addition, having a social worker on the Starting Point Silver Group may also be beneficial.

“I personally don’t feel like it needs to be a mental health role, I think just a normal social care role would be better for the social worker to sit within like a locality team and then any cases come through to social care, if case workers feel like they would need a social worker, it would go straight to that social worker but then at least they’ve got other social work teams around them, they’ve already got systems in place, they’ve got that supervision”
(Professional, 7)

Challenges in the Workforce

Several challenges relating to the workforce emerged from the evaluation. As discussed earlier in the report, although most professionals were extremely positive about the workforce, some felt that there was a lack of consistency in the delivery of support depending on the key worker with differences in the support provided, time in the office and use of the physical space. Related to this, due to short term funding streams it was increasingly difficult to maintain a skilled workforce:

“But some of them they've thankfully made reoccurring funding streams which takes a bit of pressure off, but they're only reoccurring as far as they're reoccurring as far as the money is there, so though we don't have to bid for them as such, you know it's, you just don't know, especially with current climate. And some of the bigger pots we do have to bid for. We'd have to re-bid for the monies again when it's come to the time of erm, that coming to an end, which again is, is has a massive impact in terms of staff retention, keeping hold of really good and experienced staff, erm and the impact that that has on the sort of, the quality of the service and the different workers and the changes [in support workers] for the people as well.” (Interview, Professional, 1)

It was clear that recruiting and retaining staff took a great deal of senior staff members’ time:

“I think the funding conundrum is one that, I think that, you know, it does create challenges and it does take an awful lot of time from, particularly [name of managers] time of you know, managing that team and getting that team to deliver those outcomes because you’re on that merry-go-round of recruiting and trying to retain recruits that again, I think, you know it’s how do we secure ongoing funding and not reliant on time limited funding”
(Interview, Professional, 10)

Some professionals felt that some staff required further training to improve skills, particularly around issues relating to data protection, including how sensitive data is stored on council systems and who has access to this.

“I think something that would be useful would just be more training for the staff members, not necessarily once they’ve been in the service a while, but when they first come in, the, it’s kind of like you do the eLearning that

everyone does that's like data protection, all of that stuff," (Interview, Professional, 8)

However, people working in the field were very positive about the workforce and acknowledged the difficulties of the job. It was clear. Furthermore, it is evident that the challenging nature of the role took an emotional toll on staff, requiring a great deal of resilience to remain supportive. One professional described this as *"compassion fatigue"*, another outlined the importance of remembering that staff are *"humans as well"* and to actively acknowledge the challenging nature of the work:

"Personal challenges, compassion fatigue, there is only so much you can take, like I generally don't let anything affect me, I am never offended by what people say, but you do get a bit fed up of it, day in day out, when you are going out and trying to support people to the best of your ability and they are basically saying fuck of you slag, you don't know anything for me, and you do sort of get a little bit, tired" (Interview, Professional, 6)

"And it's those sort of relationships and those connections that we make, and that's probably why we are very passionate and will stand up for any injustice because we do see it, we see the, the good, the bad, the ugly, the very ugly, the heartbreak, the loss. You know, and because we work so closely with people, we go on that journey with them. Which is great, but also, you know, we have to remember that we are humans as well and we need to consider, you know, the impact it does have on us, hence why we have reflective practice and psychological support and stuff." (Interview, Professional, 10)

Indeed, data from the observations of meetings demonstrated the sheer breadth of knowledge and support provided by key workers. It was clear that the key worker role was extremely varied providing a wide remit of support via informal (holistic person-centred) and formalised routes (safeguarding). Due to the varied nature of the settings and people, staff may be at higher risk of adverse physical and emotional events. It may be beneficial to revisit the role of the key worker to ensure the remit remains in scope and to avoid potential compassion fatigue. Examples of high-risk support provided by key workers included:

"Sent email to another participant to monitor on system and referral to safeguarding. Another to safeguarding due to someone being assaulted with a hammer, referred to the police." (Notes, Observation Meeting 6)

"Discussion of individual cases, one Person is suicidal due to death of their baby - the funeral of is soon and will be attended by key worker for support to Person. The Person struggling very badly, will need to complete welfare check if she is seen and monitored closely." (Notes, Observation Meeting 4)

"Littering / household upkeep an issue – key worker going round to empty people's bins which are full of drug paraphernalia, too dangerous for worker to clean so need to bring in specialists. Rubbish is an issue and there are worries about vermin" (Notes, Observation Meeting 16)

Interestingly, despite the impact of the service on staff there was little discussion on support for staff in the interviews with key workers. This could indicate that staff were either not aware of the support offered or did not regularly access this. Considering the challenges of the role and high staff turnover, the service would benefit from a relaunch of the support options available to staff to encourage

potential uptake. However, since the evaluation the service has now introduced reflective practice for staff, which has been shown to have had a positive impact on staff wellbeing.

Inconsistencies in the support offer from key workers created some tension between staff members due to disagreements in how support should be delivered. The emotional toll and pressures of the job exacerbated this, leading to high staff turnover, challenging working environments and at times conflict within some teams. This indicates that more needs to be done to develop a more supportive culture with avenues for staff to access when needing support or for people to report any concerns they have about staff behaviour (see ‘Recommendations’).

Protecting the Professional Identity of Embedded Worker Roles

It was clear the roles of the embedded workers were extremely valued and had a great impact on the lives of people when implemented appropriately. However, there was evidence of embedded roles which did not work as well, resulting in high staff turnover in some areas of the service. Roles that were perceived as not working well were fully embedded within Starting Point and did not hold a formal contract within their host organisation (such as the DWP worker who is funded by DWP but spends time in Starting Point). Workers who did not have formal contracts with their organisations (such as the NHS or wider council services) were unable to access appropriate data systems to support the delivery of support. This meant that the role felt similar to that of a key worker, limiting the ability of staff to provide specialist interventions. As stated elsewhere in the report, there was also some concerns around the handling of sensitive data on council systems:

“This isn’t a fault of Starting Point, but the vision for my role and the reality of it were very different....so when I took this job, you know, there were saying from the [management perspective], it was very much ‘oh we’ve now got a [name of job role]’ but I never able to provide interventions in that role. So, I had very limited resources to do my job, so I couldn’t document my notes on their systems, and I didn’t feel comfortable documenting them on the council notes... like 99.9% have a horrific history of trauma and abuse and why should that be available to council members?” (Professional, 8)

This also resulted in a lack of professional identity which was both disheartening for the individual and made it difficult for them to progress in their chosen profession - e.g. by being unable to meet certain competencies to support career development. In addition, there were some concerns around risk management and supervision when not connected to a team:

“I didn’t really feel like I was doing [name of specialist role], I felt like I was just quite a lot of the key worker... with [name of specialist role] then at least they’ve got other teams around them, they’ve already got systems in place, they’ve got that supervision. Something I really struggled with was like risk management of the work...in a normal [name of specialist team], I’d be like bottom of the barrel, then there’d be managers, whereas in Starting Point I was really high up and that meant there was kind of no one above me to manage that risk and it was quite scary” (Professional, 7)

Considering the findings, future implementation of the embedded worker role should ensure that the individual remains contracted within their host organisation with access to appropriate systems and supervision (see ‘Recommendations’). This will ensure maximum impact for both the professional and people.

Wider System Challenges

Several challenges within the wider system had an impact on service delivery. One key issue was a lack of suitable and affordable accommodation as well as supported accommodation for more complex people. Due to previous issues with rent arrears and behaviour many people had “burnt bridges” with accommodation providers but were unable to access private rented accommodation due to affordability. This often left people, and key workers, with limited options:

“I think the challenge is and this isn't just exclusive to [name of area], the housing landscape is very very different now and I think you know that everybody's, we're all on that journey together really because it is, there isn't a council house for everybody that want one or is eligible for one for whatever reason because there just isn't the supply so I think, you know we are having to consider alternatives and that's not always, that's not always easy, erm, and you know it is a really challenging environment to work in,” (Professional, 10)

“Affordability of accommodation that's massive, massive and obviously effects people that Starting Point are working with but that is a significant issue for us, it's something that were talking about probably on a daily basis to whoever will listen to us.... particularly if people are under the age of 35, it's almost impossible to secure any form of accommodation simply because it is out of reach financially...affordability, that's definitely a significant challenge.” (Interview, Professional, 11)

“...just the lack of suitable accommodation [is a key challenge]. So, private rent is an option for a lot of ours that have burned bridges, but private rent is not actually an option just because it is not affordable. There are so few supported accommodation spaces as well, the rough sleeper initiative placements were usually given to people that were found bedded down, they still are but now its on a 14 day basis, but you are not going to be able to get any meaningful day work done in 14 days.” (Interview, Professional, 6)

In addition, confusing and “subjective” medical priority criteria meant some people fell through the gaps of services:

“I think another challenge is accommodation and I think we have found sort of like when sort of, I don't know if you know but when someone has been accommodated, they can get a priority need, which is based on sort of physical, mental health, all these other things. I think we have had a number of times where that isn't clear and that's something that I sort of struggle with, sort of one guy who was type 1 diabetic and had mental health issues, he was priority need because he needed a fridge for his insulin. But then another guy who was also type 1 diabetic wasn't deemed as priority need, so there's is no sort of line for it, it is very subjective and I think that that's a struggle because we could have one person in one day, who is priority need and another one in the next day who we believe has got more needs and more need for the accommodation but isn't. I think we have a lot of fighting, not fighting but sort of, disagreements and we have to push hard on accommodation.” (Interview, Professional, 7)

Short-term funding of Starting Point was detrimental to service delivery and staff retention. Starting Point was funded through a “*jigsaw of different funding*” with different deadlines, requirements and reporting mechanisms. Short term, piecemeal funding streams and commissioning cycles made staff retention and long-term planning extremely difficult. Constantly navigating funding streams was also a great source of stress and time for senior members of staff who felt pressured to maintain staff and services:

“I think it’s necessarily what’s not working well..., the funding that we’re talking about, you know, the not long term funding opportunities, it’s all short term so the rough sleeping initiative we mentioned which funds a number of workers within the Starting Point team that was a 3 year erm funding round so you know we don’t know yet what’s gonna happen at the end of March next year when the settlement ends so I think you know that does lead to uncertainty within erm, within the service, so I think you know there’s been quite a bit of erm movement in terms of staffing and I think yeah, I don’t, obviously we do know the answer to that, we need longer term funding, settlements for things like that but you know, we can’t necessarily change that but I think I do think that presents challenges because I know [name of professional] spends an awful lot of her time recruiting, an awful lot of her time so yeah it’s not really you can’t it’s just, it’s just the environment I guess that we’re working in.” (Interview, Professional, 11)

Sadly, it was clear that locating funding for homelessness and other related services (such as substance misuse) is increasingly challenging within a constrained funding environment. Often such services were seen as “*nice to do*” rather than a priority:

“...we kind of lost the funding for it, it was described as fluffy which I found quite frustrating. It wasn’t called business, probably the better way of describing it and that was when money becomes tight, you kind, you haven’t got the, there was almost a luxury service, massively valuable, but not particularly a priority. At the moment, it feels like there is very little money about, so it’s very difficult” (Interview, Professional, 14)

Recommendations

The research identified that Starting Point was making a tremendous difference to people who had been sleeping rough or were at risk of homelessness and were vulnerable. People spoke of how the compassion and support from Starting Point staff helped them to change their lives. They especially valued how Starting Point advocated for them, shaped support to fit their needs and helped them to access services. Within the sector, Starting Point was seen as an important part of service provision to engage the most vulnerable. The positive impact of Starting Point highlights how continuing to commission the service largely in its current format is important. Notwithstanding this, our evaluation identified a number of areas which could be developed to ultimately improve the impact of Starting Point on people and the wider system. We acknowledge that it is not possible to implement all of the recommendations within the current resources of the service and that some may be feasible to implement in the near future whilst others require a longer-term approach. In addition, our evaluation demonstrates how Starting Point is an important part of the system, but it cannot provide support for this cohort alone. The importance of multidisciplinary work was clear throughout the evaluation, and several of the recommendations require system collaboration for successful implementation. The following recommendations have been sense checked and refined following to workshops with strategic leaders and the operational team.

Recommendations for Operational Delivery

Starting Point Staffing and Support

1. It is recognised across the partnership and through this evaluation how challenging and testing this type of work can be. Staff work incredibly hard in a complex and difficult environment and clearly go above and beyond to support the cohort. However, our evaluation identified some staffing challenges such as compassion fatigue, challenging workloads and conflict within some teams. It is important that all staff members feel supported and that there are options available to people to address things such as compassion fatigue and burn out as well as clear lines of communication to voice concerns. **It is recommended the service review the support in place for the team and develop clear pathways for accessing support and reporting concerns.**
2. There were concerns amongst some staff about inappropriate terminology/actions towards people in the service from other staff ,members. It is important that all staff are clear on the expectation in relation to their personal and professional conduct. **An update of the Starting Point Service Standards would be beneficial to ensure that all staff members are clear on their responsibilities.**
3. Considering the above, **it would be useful for training to be provided on CDC policy such as Whistleblowing, Code of Conduct, Grievance and complaints. As a result of the evaluation this has now been reviewed and developed, and should be revisited on a regular basis to ensure it is fit for purpose.**
4. There were concerns about whether the current induction training provides sufficient learning on skills rather than purely processes. **Therefore, it is recommended the service develops the service induction, alongside the cooperate council induction.** This could include training in trauma-informed practice and managing discharge/step down processes. **As a result of the evaluation this has now been reviewed and developed, and should be revisited on a regular basis to ensure it is fit for purpose.**

5. Although the flexibility of the service was greatly valued, there was a perceived lack of consistency in the delivery of some aspects of support and a lack of clarity from staff on expectations including time in the office which led to perceptions of inequity. **It would be useful to review the Starting Point roles and responsibilities to ensure they meet the original specification.**
6. Staff felt improvements were needed to the office space. **There is a need to consider options for operational workspace that the team can utilise and grow with. This includes extra space for co-located staff and opportunity to deliver a number of different support services and interventions.**
7. **It is important the service continue to use feedback and information from staff gathered from exit interviews and 1:1s to develop and support the staff team within the Starting Point Service.** The service should continue to explore ways to reduce the use of short-term contracts and mitigate issues relating to job insecurity, progression and wages to support workforce development.

Starting Point Service Recommendations

1. There were concerns raised about the physical space for people. To avoid inconsistencies in use of the space there needs to be clarity for staff and people about what the physical space can be used for e.g. can people have a hot drink whilst waiting to see a member of staff or need to wait outside. **It is important the service develops an accessible space that is practical for use by people, the Starting Point team and other support agencies. This should ensure agencies are under one roof to meet the multiple needs of this complex cohort.**
2. There needs to be greater clarity about the role of Starting Point in comparison to other services as this was not always well known across the system and could at times lead to tension. **It is recommended the service develop a communications strategy which will provide information to other services and providers around the different roles and functions within the Starting Point Service.** This could include a document detailing the remit of different services and their purposes across the system - showing what the distinct roles or where there was overlap would be beneficial for both the service and wider partnership. Linked to the comms strategy, Starting Point should deliver **a launch event to share new name and showcase the different areas of the service, how they can be accessed and what can be offered.**
3. Staff found it difficult helping people to be discharged from the service. A lot of support is needed to help people make progress and there was concern about what would happen when the Starting Point support was removed. **There should be a review of the Starting Point Discharge and Re-Engagement process to give a clear pathway out of the Starting Point Service but ensuring a pathway back in if needed.**
4. **Review approach to allocations and internal transitions.** Moving key workers was considered incredibly difficult and disruptive. Improving the process for people moving key workers is recommended.
5. **Explore options for supporting people to become more independent by providing crucial skills and improving people's confidence in managing their lives** including in life administration skills e.g. making appointments, managing utility bills and time management especially in relation to attending appointments.

6. **There needs to be clear communication between people and allocated workers about decisions being made around support and accommodation.** Information should be shared around outcomes from referrals and meetings concerning people. Where possible, those supported by the service should be invited to be part of that process. There could be scope in involving people in relevant meetings about them.
7. **Ensure the Starting Point service is accessible to all.** This includes those from ethnic minority groups, considering language barrier, sex worker and any other excluded groups.

Data Insight and Systems

1. Although the team collects data from the Homelessness Outcome Star, it was difficult to access monitoring data across the service population. **Therefore, a recommendation is for the service to ensure they have data monitoring systems in place that ensures relevant data is collected and stored in ways which are usable.**
2. Data on numbers of referrals made and interventions received was difficult to access. Consider reporting and recording systems to support the monitoring of service data. Whilst data is currently being collated, it is not in one central space and relies on input onto spreadsheets from a member of the Starting Point Team. **It is recommended that the data monitoring system is reviewed to ensure it is accessible and recorded in one place to support future commissioning decisions.**
3. There were concerns from some staff over the use of council systems for sensitive data. **Since the evaluation the service has updated its consent and privacy policy as well as its retention schedule to streamline this process. This should be regularly monitored and kept up to date.**
4. Longer-term it would be valuable to explore whether it would be possible to be on the same case management system as social care services to enable better sharing of information.

Recommendations for the External System and Wider Council

1. It is important to improve how staff are embedded from other services to sustain the partnership model. Embedded staff appeared to work better when the person kept most of their role based with the original service - this allowed them to continue to have their professional peer support and feel connected to their profession but having a couple of days a week based within the Starting Point Service. A strength of Starting Point is bringing other services to people but for this model to be sustainable, staff need to be embedded well and remain connected to their contracting organisation with access to appropriate systems. In addition, **the challenges of the embedded worker role suggest that future implementation should ensure that the individual remains contracted within their host organisation with access to appropriate systems and supervision.**
2. There was a lack of cooking and laundry facilities for people living on the streets or in some types of accommodation such as B&Bs/Hotels. **Within the system, there needs consideration of how to provide facilities which support people with meeting their basic needs independently.** For example, working with hostels to provide sessions when people can utilise facilities. It is appreciated that this carries both costs and also safeguarding risks so it requires longer-term consideration of how to design a service which can support people with accessing living facilities.

3. Starting Point relies on being able to bring services to people especially initially in people's journey e.g. bringing the DWP to Starting Point. This relies on services being willing to free up resources to offer targeted support to people supported by Starting Point. This does not necessarily require more resources but does **require other services to be generous and be able to consider working differently to meet people's specific needs.**
4. There were concerns around stigma related to homelessness across wider council services and an expectation to *"house people as quickly as possible"* without consideration of the wider drivers of homelessness. **It may be beneficial to use the evaluation findings and stories from those with lived experience to relaunch the service to wider partners across the council, focusing on committees working at a strategic level.** This could form part of the comms strategy.

Recommendations for Strategic Delivery

1. **There should be further consideration of the different strategic groups, their purpose, attendance and frequency of meetings as there was sometimes low attendance by some partners.** It may be beneficial to **relaunch the Starting Point Silver Group** by revisiting the aims and objectives of the group and to ensure activities will support the delivery of these objectives. This should include a shared mission statement and visual identity with clear connection between other council groups (such as the Bronze and Gold levels) to ensure appropriate information cascades down. **In addition, developing the representation of the group to include more health partners and those working at a strategic level** who can push the service within their organisations will support the mobilisation of knowledge into policy and practice. This could include representatives from the **ICB, mental health and social care** to help mitigate some of the challenges identified in this evaluation.
2. Linked to above, **it would be useful to revisit the Starting Point Alliance agreement** to develop a shared agreement outlining roles, responsibilities, and contributions and set baseline expectations for attendance and engagement.
3. Despite the Starting Point Silver Group identifying prevention as a key area of focus in the interviews there was a lack of action plan to drive change forward. In addition, returning rough sleepers are a key challenge for the service. **It would be beneficial for the Starting Point alliance to review its approach to prevention and create an action plan to move the service from a reactive to a proactive service. This should align with current work being undertaken within the council.**
4. Stigma relating to homelessness was identified as a key issue across the council. **Reducing stigma should be a key priority for the Starting Point Alliance and the group should work together to create an action plan to improve this.** This could include the production of materials such as videos, a podcast and council e-learning, which highlight people's journey.
5. Starting Point is supporting people with complex needs to sustain living in independent accommodation, access services and have more stability. The strength of the service is having the flexibility within a commissioned service to shape support to individual needs for a number of years. It is key that any commissioned service needs to provide a service with the scope to provide longer-term, intensive flexible support as it takes considerable time to support people to make changes. Linked to the point above, **it is important that the wider**

council is made aware of the time it takes to support people as well as the challenges for staff when considering outcomes from the service.

6. There is a need for greater clarity on the different roles and interventions provided by Starting Point for internal and external partners - it's more than getting people accommodation but is about advocacy, and supporting people to access services to address their health and social care needs to enable them to sustain housing and prevent deterioration. Similar to the previous recommendation, **it may be useful to relaunch the study to partners to ensure everyone is clear on the aims and remit of the service.** This could be underpinned by a coproduction approach which allows partners to be able to shape the service moving forward and feel their contribution is valued which may support potential buy-in. **To support this, it may be useful to create plain-English materials explaining; who the service supports (e.g. homeless, at risk, complex needs), how to access the service, what support is available and how to refer (including a flowchart with touch points along the journey)**
7. **There is a need to develop the health inclusion support offer.** This should be underpinned by a system approach which involves both housing and health practitioners. Despite investment and positive outcomes from the service in the removal of barriers to accessing services for the cohort, significant barriers remain. It was suggested that convening MDTs with health and housing partners to discuss complex cases experiencing barriers in the health service could support better collaboration.
8. Linked to the above, **there is a clear gap in services for people who struggle with their mental health but are not considered severe or stable enough to access mental health services.** There is a need to develop a specialist mental health service or at least 'light touch' interventions for people with substance misuse issues which delivers appropriate services that meet where people are, this is particularly in terms of psychological therapies support. It may be beneficial to explore if/how other geographical areas have managed this. It is appreciated that this won't necessarily be longer-term psychological therapy but could be something short-term to support people somewhat with their mental health.
9. There was not always suitable housing accommodation available and Starting Point is dependent on what accommodation is available in the system. Investing in suitable housing options for the population was important to avoid them being housed in inappropriate accommodation which may be detrimental to people progressing. We acknowledge this is a wider system issue which Starting Point is unable to address in isolation. **The service (alongside system partners) should continue lobbying for the development of appropriate housing in the borough.**
10. Starting Point relies on external short-term funding. This contributes to uncertainty within the service and staff turnover. **The strategic alliance/commissioners need to consider how to maximise funding especially concurrent funding adopting a more 'alliance' commissioning model.** This involves a more collaborative approach where multiple organisations, including both commissioners and providers, work together under a single contract to deliver services, sharing risks and responsibilities.

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